

Euphresco

Final Report

For more information and guidance on completion and submission of the report contact the Euphresco Call Secretariat (bgiovani@euphresco.net).

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Potential for using IPM tools to control or eradicate box tree moth (<i>Cydalima perspectalis</i>) incursions
License

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2. Short project report

2.1 Short executive summary

The box tree moth, *Cydalima perspectalis*, is an invasive insect native to East Asia. After it was first detected in Europe in 2006, it spread rapidly across most European countries as well as the Caucasus and Iran, causing severe damage to both ornamental and natural boxwood (*Buxus* spp.). Many affected areas experienced extensive defoliation and long-term decline of boxwood plantings and native boxwood forests. Management often required repeated applications of conventional insecticides or biological products such as *Bacillus thuringiensis*. Wild stands of *Buxus sempervirens* in several regions were heavily affected, raising ecological concerns.

The moth was first found in North America in 2018 in Toronto, Ontario, and later detected in 2021 in western New York. By late 2025, established infestations were known from at least ten U.S. states. Boxwood is widely used as an ornamental plant across the United States, Canada, and Europe. In Europe, it is also an important component of natural forests, which increases the economic and ecological significance of the pest. Although reports exist of feeding on *Euonymus* or *Ilex* species, extensive European experience and recent Canadian research indicate that damage and feeding are restricted exclusively to *Buxus* species.

This Euphresco project was initiated to support the development and evaluation of integrated pest management tools for *Cydalima perspectalis* to improve control strategies for the newly invaded regions of North America and in Europe. The overall goal of the project was to develop and assess methods for protecting boxwood in ornamental plantings, nurseries, and native stands, including tools that may be deployed on an area-wide basis to support eradication or containment campaigns and to safeguard high-value and at-risk landscapes. The project aimed to strengthen detection and monitoring methods; expand understanding of the pest's biology, ecology, and behaviour; evaluate mating disruption; develop mass-rearing capabilities; assess classical and conservation biological control options; study microbial and chemical control treatments; develop tools and recommendations to address regulatory and phytosanitary issues; and examine the feasibility of the sterile insect technique as an additional control tool. Another important goal was to develop networking and collaborative research between European researchers who have more than a decade of experience with the pest, and those in North America, where the invasion is more recent.

The consortium included 17 institutions from nine countries and involved more than 40 participants from regulatory, academic, and applied research settings. From 2023 to 2026, the group held three technical meetings to present research results to exchange information and to build collaborative research and communication networks. Over the course of the project, a total of 85 research, extension and national plant protection organization regulatory outputs were recorded. These consisted of 18 peer reviewed journal articles, 30 grey-literature reports, 33 scientific or stakeholder presentations, and 6 outreach media pieces. In addition, 13 publications and other outreach output are in progress or planned for release after the project period, including a comprehensive review summarizing the global pest status of box tree moth and the available management tools .

Project activities covered the full range of objectives: 1) Work on detection trapping produced improvements in trap performance by evaluation of how pheromone and lure combinations function under field conditions and evaluated female lures; 2) Biological and ecological studies generated new information on phenological timing, dispersal and reproduction; 3) Mating disruption trials in different landscapes showed that the tactic can be effective when used early and in large enough areas; 4) Mass-rearing research resulted in development of an artificial diet to support studies in insecticide evaluation, behaviour, and biological control; 5) Exploration in the native ranges of BTM in east Asia resulted in the discovery of several new species of promising species of candidate parasitoids for implementation of classical biological control programs and also examined natural enemy complexes in Europe and North America; 6) Evaluation of microbial and chemical insecticide treatments including Btk formulations, for efficacy and optimal treatment 7) Exploratory work on radiation biology identified dose ranges suitable for evaluating sterile insect technique applications; 8) Extensive dissemination of research results and biological details about BTM was communicated broadly throughout member countries by multiple means of medias and information exchange.

Taken together, the project resulted in a coordinated effort to improve understanding and management of *Cydalima perspectalis* in the respective member countries. The information and tools developed through the project support earlier detection, more consistent containment efforts, and improved management planning for agencies, nurseries, and others responsible for protecting boxwood resources.

2.2 Project goals and objectives

The goal of this project was to develop and evaluate IPM tools to protect boxwood in ornamental plantings, nurseries, and native stands. Development of additional IPM tools for possible use on an area-wide basis will be important to support eradication or for slow-the-spread campaigns and will also be important for protection of nursery production, native boxwood forests and at-risk ornamental landscapes.

The box tree moth (BTM), *Cydalima perspectalis*, is an insect of East Asian origin that was first detected in Europe in 2006 and rapidly spread across most European countries to the Caucasus and Iran, devastating ornamental and natural boxwood stands and causing severe economic losses. The pest was first found in North America in September 2018 in Toronto, Ontario, Canada, and in 2021 in Niagara County, New York, USA, with subsequent detections in at least nine U.S. states as of late 2025—including Delaware, Kentucky, Massachusetts, Maryland, Michigan, New York, Ohio, Pennsylvania, Virginia, and West Virginia—posing serious risks to the North American ornamental horticulture industry. In Europe, Canada and part of the U.S. this rapid spread has resulted in extensive defoliation and mortality of residential, commercial and culturally significant heritage boxwood plantings along with impacts to native boxwood forests.

The European experience demonstrated the pest's capacity for fast dispersal and high reproductive potential, as well as the difficulty of managing outbreaks without a coordinated regulatory framework or integrated pest management (IPM) tools. The information from the BTM infestation in Europe provided valuable insights into the potential consequences should the pest become widely established in North America and highlighted the challenges posed by the absence of a coordinated regulatory framework to slow its spread. As BTM emerged in North America, regulatory authorities and industry stakeholders

similarly lacked region-specific information needed to support rapid response, assess the feasibility of eradication, and guide management decisions.

This Euphresco project therefore offered an important opportunity for North American and European researchers to collaborate, exchange biological and management information, and accelerate the evaluation of existing control tools while supporting the development of new ones. Through networking and coordinated research activities, the project helped generate information that would benefit stakeholders across the Euphresco network.

Overall, the project achieved its intended goals. It produced essential scientific data and practical management tools needed to strengthen regulatory frameworks, inform operational decision-making, and support stakeholders in detecting, managing, and limiting the spread of BTM. The results contributed directly to responses to new detections, bolstered containment and slow-the-spread efforts, and provided a foundation for future investments in biological control, mating disruption technologies, and additional plant protection tools.

The objectives of this project were organized in 10 objectives (as work packages) to:

1. **Develop enhanced monitoring methods (WP-2):** For rapid response to BTM outbreaks in newly invaded areas by identifying effective trap and pheromone or kairomone combinations for catching adult male and female moths under field situations.
2. **Conduct studies to investigate biology, population ecology, and behaviour (WP-3):** Improve understanding of BTM life cycle, population dynamics and behavioural traits.
3. **Evaluate the application of mating disruption (WP-4):** For protection of ornamental, native and natural boxwood forests, and nursery crops of boxwood, and for use as a key tool in slow-the-spread and eradication campaigns.
4. **Develop efficient mass-rearing methods on artificial diet (WP-5):** To support research on pesticide treatments, the sterile insect technique, biological control, and behavioural studies.
5. **Investigate the potential for classical biological control of BTM (WP-6):** Conduct foreign exploration, establish quarantine cultures, research parasitoid biology, and perform non-target host range testing.
6. **Conduct natural enemy surveys and evaluate the impacts of native parasitoids and predators (WP-7):** Assess contributions of indigenous natural enemies to BTM population regulation.
7. **Investigate control treatments with Btk, baculoviruses and chemical pesticide treatments (WP-8):** Evaluate efficacy of biological and chemical control options.
8. **Develop regulatory treatments, systems approaches and BTM phytosanitary measures (WP-9):** Safeguard shipments of nursery stock via improved phytosanitary protocols.
9. **Conduct studies to determine the radiation biology of BTM (WP-10):** Evaluate the feasibility of the sterile insect technique.

10. Dissemination of results and information exchange. (WP-11)

2.3 Description of the main activities

The Box Tree Moth–IPM Working Group implemented a coordinated programme of 10 research areas (work packages) aimed at strengthening international capacity for the detection, management, and potential eradication of *Cydalima perspectalis*. The consortium brought together 17 participating institutions from eight countries and engaged more than 40 scientific experts across the research, regulatory, and applied plant-health communities. Activities were carried out between 2023 and 2026, during which the consortium convened three full technical meetings to review progress, exchange research findings, and plan collaborative actions.

The main activities focused on establishing a forum for scientific exchange and strengthening cooperation among national plant protection organisations, universities, and research institutes from several BTM affected countries. The meetings provided an opportunity for partners to present ongoing work to compare methodologies, provide critical feedback and inspire research collaborations.

A major outcome of the work addressed biological control and natural enemy research. Partners conducted surveys for native and adventive parasitoids and entomopathogens in both Europe and North America and exchanged findings on species with potential relevance to classical and conservation biological control. Collaborations were established to assess agents originating from Asia, including detailed studies on parasitoid biology, host range non-target evaluation, and rearing. These activities support the planned goal of preparing a petition for release of *Eriborus* sp. (to date, the most promising BTM parasitoid discovered through foreign exploration) for implementation of classical biological control in North America and may be used to support requesting permits for redistribution of *Eriborus* adventively established in parts of Europe.

Progress was also made in the evaluation of pheromone-based mating disruption (MD). Trials carried out in several countries in individual gardens, natural habitats, and larger scale area-wide trials in urban landscapes provided comparative data on formulation performance, treatment scale, and integration with microbial insecticides. The exchange of protocols and field experiences contributed to improved understanding of operational requirements for MD deployment in varying environmental contexts and also highlighted the need for these products to be registered in both North American and European markets.

Further work focused on detection and monitoring, including trap-performance comparisons, pheromone dose optimisation, sampling-area estimation, and the assessment of attractant combinations. These activities supported the refinement of surveillance schemes and the identification of early infestation indicators. Complementary studies on ecology, phenology, and behaviour—including analysis of flight activity, mating dynamics, and developmental timing—provided essential information to guide control scheduling and improve early intervention.

The consortium also advanced research on chemical and biological plant-protection products, including the evaluation of Btk formulations, insecticide efficacy trials, and regulatory treatment studies for nursery stock. These activities aimed to define effective treatment windows, assess product performance under diverse conditions, and support national phytosanitary frameworks. In parallel, substantial progress was made in mass-rearing techniques and artificial diet development, facilitating the reliable production of BTM for experimental purposes and for future work on SIT and biological control.

Overall, through the consortium a successful coordinated, multi-country research framework was established. Through regular scientific exchange, the consortium enhanced knowledge on key IPM components, facilitated joint research initiatives, and strengthened the scientific basis for evidence-driven strategies to manage *Cydalima perspectalis* across participating countries.

List of work packages:

- **WP1:** Project management and co-ordination (not covered in this report)
- **WP2:** Develop enhanced monitoring methods
- **WP3:** Conduct studies to investigate biology, population ecology, and behaviour
- **WP4:** Evaluate the application of mating disruption
- **WP5:** Develop efficient mass-rearing methods on artificial diet
- **WP6:** Investigate the potential for classical biological control of BTM
- **WP7:** Conduct natural enemy surveys and evaluate the impacts of native parasitoids, predators, and entomopathogens
- **WP8:** Investigate control treatments with Btk, baculoviruses and chemical pesticide treatments
- **WP9:** Develop regulatory treatments, systems approaches and BTM phytosanitary measures to safeguard shipments of nursery stock
- **WP10:** Conduct studies to determine the radiation biology of BTM to evaluate the feasibility of the sterile insect technique
- **WP11:** Dissemination of results and information exchange (reported in Outreach)

2.4 Main results

WP2: Develop enhanced monitoring methods

Work under WP2 advanced the development of detection and monitoring tools essential for tracking box tree moth (BTM) in both newly invaded and established areas. Work in heritage boxwood gardens in the UK revealed that traps placed in shade consistently captured more moths than those in full sun, an observation that was included in recommendations for the detection trapping program in North America. Release–recapture experiments conducted in Croatia demonstrated that male moth attraction to

pheromone-baited traps declined sharply beyond 100–200 meters, and statistical modelling across multiple trials showed that each trap effectively sampled an area of roughly 0.5 hectares. These findings provide concrete guidance for designing efficient surveillance networks. Parallel evaluations of pheromone lure loadings showed that higher doses, within the 3–6 mg range, increased trap captures compared with 1 mg lures. This pattern held across both delta and bucket-style traps in multi-year trials. Trap comparisons revealed that bucket-style unitraps often capture more than ten times the number of moths caught in other traps. Because unitraps may attract pollinators and are restricted in sensitive habitats, alternative traps were also assessed for program use in these areas in the U.S. Large delta traps baited with higher-dose lures performed similarly to unitraps but with minimal bycatch, making them suitable for sites where unitraps cannot be used. Other work in North America evaluated trap modifications designed to reduce bee bycatch using alternative adhesives and clear trap bodies. Clear unitraps and green traps performed equally well compared to yellow and white bicolour traps for moth capture but attracted fewer pollinators. These findings supported making recommendations to the U.S. BTM program for trap selection, density, and deployment.

WP3: Conduct studies to investigate biology, population ecology, and behaviour

WP3 produced biological, ecological, and phenological information across multiple BTM infested areas in North America. Long-term monitoring established consistent seasonal population patterns, with two primary generations per year in the Great Lakes regions and Northern U.S. states and a third generation in warmer areas to the south. Overwintered larvae became active as early as late March in southern areas of Europe and North America, and adult flight peaks occurred from late June through July in the Great Lakes region and again from late August through September, with late-season activity extending into October at some locations. Degree-day modelling showed that simple temperature-based models accurately predicted adult emergence and early larval feeding.

Genetic analyses of North American populations revealed a single mitochondrial haplotype, indicating that the North American invasion likely originated from a single lineage. This population is distinct from the USDA laboratory colony collected in Croatia indicating different population lineages. Laboratory studies refined key parameters for larval development, overwintering success, reproductive timing, and fecundity, and flight performance tests confirmed that adults are capable of sustained long-distance dispersal, with maximum recorded distances reaching approximately 15 kilometres and average speeds exceeding 1 m/s. Behavioural studies showed that courtship and copulation occur exclusively at night, predominantly in the early scotophase, and last about one hour; females exhibited only a short calling periods near dusk. Host specificity trials in both Europe and Canada further showed that larvae readily fed on boxwood but could not complete development on *Euonymus*, confirming the latter's unsuitability as an alternative host.

WP4: Evaluate the application of mating disruption

WP4 demonstrated that pheromone-based mating disruption (MD) can effectively suppress BTM populations and protect boxwood across a wide range of habitats. In Germany, MD applied in a large formal garden produced complete trap shutdown (defined as the reduction or elimination of insect captures in a pheromone trap) in disrupted areas as a measure of the efficacy of the MD application and substantially reduced larval densities and feeding damage, with the strongest effects occurring in more isolated parts of the property. Multi-year replicated trials in Croatian urban environments achieved consistent reductions of approximately 95–96% in adult trap captures, accompanied by major decreases in larval and pupal densities and significant reductions in damage ranging from ~30% to 80% depending on year and site configuration. In the United Kingdom, MD use in a historic garden resulted in an approximately 80% reduction in seasonal damage and allowed gardeners to reduce their typical number of Btk sprays from eight per season to three. Additional UK trials on oviposition-detering volatiles demonstrated an ~80% reduction in caterpillar abundance later in the season, indicating that complementary semiochemical tools may augment MD. MD applied in a natural boxwood stand along the Thames demonstrated feasibility even in natural boxwood forested areas. In the United States, a large area-wide MD program in western New York combined with coordinated Btk applications produced near-complete suppression of male captures, 92–100% reductions in larval infestations, and 76–100% reductions in feeding damage. Some nearby untreated sites recorded no BTM detections despite proximity to treated areas, suggesting that natural movement within urban neighbourhoods may be more limited than previously assumed and that coordinated neighbourhood-scale MD can create highly effective suppression zones. These are positive signs that local area-wide control strategies can be effective if a BTM population is treated in the first few years of detection. Collectively, results across regions show that MD performs best when deployed prior to the first annual adult flight, over large continuous areas, and in combination with Btk targeted to early larval instars.

WP5: Develop efficient mass rearing methods on artificial diet

WP5 delivered an effective artificial diet and rearing system capable of supporting full BTM development while greatly reducing the need for fresh boxwood in BTM rearing programs. Early studies showed that previously published diets supported larval feeding but not normal pupation, and that adding dried or extracted boxwood material did not improve performance, likely because essential cues were lost during processing or insufficient quantities of dried boxwood were added. A key breakthrough came when larvae reared on a non-optimal base diet successfully pupated after being transferred to fresh boxwood, demonstrating that certain necessary components were only present in boxwood and that the quantity of boxwood material in previously tested diets needed optimization with mixture of other components in the diet. Building on this, the USDA-APHIS-PPQ team evaluated several diet mixtures with varying amounts of boxwood powder and protein components. By 2024, a fully functional diet enabling complete development was achieved, and by 2025 it was optimized for routine use. The diet uses approximately 88% less plant material than traditional methods while producing insects with pupal weights and developmental success comparable to those reared on live boxwood. The resulting rearing system is cost-effective, scalable, and suitable for large-scale research and regulatory applications.

In total, the USDA mass-rearing has produced more than 56,000 insects to support pesticide evaluations, biological studies, SIT research, virus work, biocontrol trials, and outreach. Improvements to rearing

container design, transfer timing, and handling of early instars increased survival and reduced cannibalism, and a new colony line was established from a Massachusetts collection which is a different source population from the colony established from BTM collected in Croatia.

WP6: Investigate the potential for classical biological control of BTM

Work completed under WP6 evaluated the parasitoid *Eriborus* sp. as a candidate for classical biological control. Laboratory host-specificity experiments showed that while *Eriborus* occasionally attacked certain non-target Crambidae and Pyralidae, it did not develop successfully in any non-target species, whereas parasitism and successful development were consistent on BTM. Choice tests demonstrated a clear preference for BTM larvae. Studies on parasitoid biology revealed that females can live over 30 days, with some surviving up to 60 days, and that parasitism activity increases gradually after emergence, reaching high levels by day seven. *Eriborus* successfully parasitized all larval instars, although egression always occurred from 5th-instar BTM larvae.

Chemical ecology tests showed attraction to BTM frass odours, indicating potential cues for host location. Field surveys in Germany and Switzerland identified established adventive *Eriborus* populations with parasitism rates as high as 68% in Germany and 32% in Switzerland, and confirmed synchrony between parasitoid and host, with two generations per year and overwintering occurring in first-instar larvae. Foreign exploration revealed multiple parasitoids associated with BTM in Asia, with *Eriborus* being one of the most abundant in South Korea. Laboratory investigations of *Dolichogenidea* sp. and *Peribaea* sp. showed that these two species have high potential to be effective BTM parasitoids with parasitism rates ranging for 71-92% and greater than 60% respectively. Preliminary host specificity tests showed successful development only on BTM for *Dolichogenidea* sp. while more work on developing stable laboratory rearing methods for *Peribaea* sp. is needed to conduct host range testing for this species. Taken together, these results strongly support *Eriborus* sp. as a highly specific, biologically compatible candidate for classical biological control with the potential to effectively control BTM if established and that *Dolichogenidea* sp. is also a very promising species as an additional classical biological control agent.

WP7: Conduct natural enemy surveys and evaluate impacts of native parasitoids, predators, and entomopathogens

WP7 surveyed natural enemies of BTM across multiple European regions and assessed their potential contributions to biological control. Surveys in southeastern England recorded overall parasitism rates below 1% but revealed the presence of *Pimpla rufipes*, adding another species in addition to earlier detections of the generalist tachinids *Pseudoperichaeta nigrolineata* and *Stenomalina communis* found parasitizing BTM. Although these species currently exert minimal pressure on BTM populations, their documentation contributes to an expanding baseline understanding of the emerging natural enemy complex. Extensive sampling in Spain (Navarre) between 2021 and 2024 yielded thousands of larvae and documented multiple entomopathogenic fungi as well as baculovirus isolates recovered from natural BTM populations for the first time. Several viral genotypes showed high pathogenicity and strong trans-generational persistence, underscoring the potential for microbial control. Screening of Bt proteins and native Bt strains identified several Cry proteins and isolates with strong larvicidal activity. Laboratory studies in Italy demonstrated that *Exorista larvarum* readily oviposits on BTM larvae and develops

successfully, suggesting potential as a conservation biological control agent where the species is naturally present.

Additional work incorporated detailed assessments of *Trichogramma* egg parasitoids and newly documented tachinid associations. Laboratory assays in Canada evaluated four *Trichogramma* species—*T. brassicae*, *T. platneri*, *T. minutum*, and *T. ostrinae*—against BTM eggs and found that all four species parasitized BTM successfully, with *T. ostrinae* achieving the highest egg mortality and successful parasitoid emergence. These results confirm that *Trichogramma* spp. are biologically compatible with BTM and may serve as augmentative biocontrol candidates. Meanwhile, field collections in Croatia yielded the first documented case of *Nemorilla floralis* parasitism on BTM, with estimated parasitism rates of 1.2–2.4%. This widely distributed Palearctic tachinid had no prior recorded association with BTM, and its detection indicates that additional natural enemy relationships are likely to emerge as the invasion continues. Collectively, WP7 findings show that although natural enemy pressure remains generally low, significant new discoveries—including *N. floralis*, pathogenic baculoviruses, effective Bt isolates, *Exorista* oviposition, and the demonstrated compatibility of *Trichogramma* spp.—provide potential components for future IPM and conservation biological control approaches.

WP8: Investigate control treatments with Btk, baculoviruses, and chemical pesticides

Results from WP8 confirmed the high effectiveness of *Bacillus thuringiensis* var. *kurstaki* (Btk) showed that properly timed applications produced >90% larval mortality within five days in field trials, with laboratory tests showing complete mortality within 96 hours. Efficacy was highest against early instars (L1–L2), with decreased performance against later stages, underscoring the importance of phenology-based timing.

Work under this WP also validated a control protocol integrating Btk with pheromone-trap monitoring, field scouting, and phenology models. This protocol was effective across multiple years and sites and showed minimal short-term impact on non-target Lepidoptera communities.

Additional microbiological research under WP8 included larval susceptibility assays, assessment of environmental factors affecting Btk performance, and evaluation of microbial control compatibility with broader IPM frameworks. These findings establish Btk as a reliable, environmentally compatible tool within integrated management strategies for BTM.

WP9: Develop regulatory treatments, systems approaches, and BTM phytosanitary measures

Work completed under WP9 provided the efficacy and residual-performance data needed to establish regulatory control tools to safeguard the movement of boxwood nursery stock. Extensive laboratory, semi-field, and field trials evaluated multiple active ingredients, with diamide insecticides consistently delivering the strongest and most durable control. Direct foliar applications showed that Chlorantraniliprole performed best overall, achieving 95–98% mortality during the first 7–35 days after application, maintaining roughly 89–90% control at 49 days, and remaining effective in tests extending to 63 days. Cyantraniliprole provided similarly high early control—93–97% at 7–21 days. Drench applications of both of these diamides did not perform as well as foliar application with mortality ranging from 50–75% over the same sampling intervals after treatment. Tank mixtures such as cyclaniliprole +

flonicamid and spinetoram + sulfoxaflor produced exceptionally high early mortality (approaching 99–100%), but efficacy declined more rapidly over time, falling to ranging from 30–74% by 35–49 days.

Other chemistries, including tolfenpyrad, dinotefuran, and spinosad, delivered moderate control with shorter treatment windows; spinosad provided near-immediate mortality but lost efficacy quickly as residues degraded. Field residue trials that targeted mixed larval instars confirmed these overall patterns, with chlorantraniliprole and methoxyfenozide producing 97–100% mortality across instars and bifenthrin demonstrating high performance at elevated rates. Lambda-cyhalothrin performed well early but showed reduced persistence possibly due to wash-off in wet conditions or lowered efficacy with hot weather. Evaluation of several adjuvants showed several products that improved canopy coverage and uniformity with better penetration and adherence to the waxy leaves of boxwood.

Collectively, these results defined practical treatment windows suitable for operational nursery use and directly informed the development of the United States regulatory treatment protocol for boxwood production nurseries, which specifies which insecticides and rates allow safe plant movement with up to three weeks after treatment and thereby reduces the risk of long-distance BTM spread through commercial trade.

WP10: Conduct studies to determine the radiation biology of BTM to evaluate feasibility of SIT

WP10 established the radiation dose ranges necessary to sterilize BTM while preserving sufficient adult vigour for sterile insect technique (SIT) applications. Experiments on nearly mature pupae showed that females were fully sterilized at approximately 130 Gy, whereas males required a higher of 200 Gy to achieve high rates of sterility. Male fertility declined sharply with increasing dose, and eggs produced by females mated with irradiated males displayed very low hatch rates at moderate treatment levels. In Lepidoptera which exhibit inherited sterility, the offspring of irradiated males were also assessed, revealing extremely low fertility—generally near zero to only a few percent—when their fathers were exposed to at least 200 Gy. These findings identify a potential operational dose ranging between 130–200 Gy that balances sterility and mating performance and allowing incorporation of inherited sterility. For future development of SIT as an IPM control tool, the next steps would be to evaluate in field cages and by small field releases in isolated areas to refine dose rates and to evaluate overflooding release rates.

WP11: Dissemination of results and information exchange

The consortium comprised 17 institutions from nine countries, involving more than 40 scientists representing regulatory agencies, universities, and research organisations. Activities were implemented between 2023 and 2026, during which the group held three international technical meetings that served as our means for sharing research progress, and networking to foster collaboration. Over the course of the project, a total of 105 outputs were identified. This includes 17 peer-reviewed journal articles, 30 grey literature reports or information sheets, 35 research presentations at scientific and stakeholder meetings, and 7 additional media or social-media outreach events. In addition, there are 12 planned journal articles currently in preparation. Furthermore, participants are planning to create a review article about the current status of the box tree moth as a worldwide pest of boxwood and prospects for sustainable integrated

pest management programs. This would be the first comprehensive review article of this kind since box tree moth first was detected in Europe and then in North America.

2.5 Conclusions and recommendations to policy makers / end-users

The project has provided comprehensive understanding of box tree moth (BTM) biology, pest status and management across different regions, demonstrating the value of coordinated international research. Collaboration between North American and European partners strengthened the scientific foundations for decision-making, enabled the rapid exchange of biological and operational information, and accelerated the assessment of monitoring, suppression, and regulatory tools that can help safeguard boxwood nursery production and the nursery trade, protect heritage landscape and natural boxwood forests, and provided technical information to support early detection and area-wide emergency response.

The practical value of the project's outputs was demonstrated during a 2025 detection in the United States. Using phenology modelling and information on local life stages generated through the project, USDA scientists and state partners were able to rapidly initiate treatment and monitoring actions based on new information about BTM in North America. This response illustrated that the modelling framework and operational guidance developed through the project can serve as the standard approach for addressing future incursions and confirmed the importance of linking research outputs directly to operational use.

Recommendations for policy makers and end-users:

- Advance a petition for release of *Eriborus* sp. as a new classical biological control agent for BTM in North America.
- Assess the possibility of relocating *Eriborus* sp. from Switzerland and Germany to the rest of Europe and to Western Asia to more rapidly increase the spread of this parasitoid.
- Continue biological studies and rearing requirements along with non-target host range testing of *Dolichogenidea* sp. and *Peribaea* sp. to evaluate their potential as additional biological control agents,
- Document the establishment and impacts of released biological control agents for at least five years post-release.
- Maintain and expand support for ongoing IPM tool development and extension resources, coordinated with evaluation of the potential impacts of new and existing insecticides on *Eriborus* sp. establishment and levels of control achieved.
- Develop recommendations for insecticides that can be used and the timing of applications in areas where *Eriborus* sp. has been established.
- Support continued development of microbial tools and exploration of new peptide-based targets.

- Incorporate sustainable pest management and insecticide resistance-management principles into regulatory and operational programmes and for BTM control in residential and commercial landscape and for ornamental nursery production.
- Develop operational area-wide population suppression and rapid-response protocols for new detections based on phenological models and available tools.
- Encourage government and industry support for registration of mating disruption products for North American and European markets.
- Integrate phenology models into operational planning and extension guidance for growers, the public, and official control programmes.

Research priorities identified during the project include the following:

- Determine the minimum effective treatment area required for successful mating disruption.
- Determine what degree of isolation from boxwood hosts is needed for area-wide treatment to be most effective and how landscape or ornamental nursery isolation or proximity to infested boxwood affect treatment and safeguarding options.
- Understand where females mate in fragmented or patchy landscapes and whether host presence influences mating behaviour.
- Determine short and long-distance dispersal patterns and natural movement behavior of BTM in different landscapes in order to optimize the use of MD and other area wide control tools
- Determine which mating disruption mechanisms (competitive attraction, plume masking, or male desensitization) dominate in order to optimize MD dispenser type, number, and release characteristics for maximum efficacy and to aid in product development.
- Refine and climate-specific validation of BTM phenology models to support precise timing insecticide treatments and use of MD.
- Evaluate BTM phenology and climatic requirements of *Eriborus* sp., *Dolichogenidea* sp. ,and *Peribaea* sp. to determine probability of success against BTM in North American and European regions,
- Add cessation of diapause of overwintering BTM larvae in hibernacula to predictive phenology models in order to optimize insecticidal treatment of these stages when they become active.
- Establish the window of time after detection active control must begin to maximize the likelihood of local eradication.
- Define the duration of treatment and post-treatment monitoring needed to confirm eradication.
- Conduct needed research to develop insecticide resistance management protocols.

- Evaluate and evaluate IPM control methods that are compatible with biological control in areas where new classical biological control agents have become established.
- Determine if there is any genetic resistance to BTM feeding within boxwood varieties.

3. Outreach

3.1 Achieved output / dissemination

3.1.1 Article(s) for publication in journals

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3.1.3 Events

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Gallizia S, Francati S, Dindo ML, Ferracini C. 2025b. Assessing the potential of *Exorista larvarum* (L.) as a biocontrol agent against the invasive box tree moth *Cydalima perspectalis* (Walker). Presented at: European PhD Network "Insect Science" – XVI Annual Meeting; 2025 Nov 12–14; Florence. p. 26. Oral presentation. Gilrein D, Dyer J. 2026. Boxwood: a comparison of adjuvants. Presented at: Seeing Things from a New *perspectalis*: Methods for Managing the Invasive Box Tree Moth; 2026; Sheraton Harrisburg Hershey Hotel, Harrisburg, PA. 8:25 AM.

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3.1.4 Other Visibility actions

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Simmons G. 2023. Potential for using IPM tools to control or eradicate box tree moth incursion (BTM-IPM). Retrieved 2026 Apr 28. <https://drop.euphresco.net/data/2f507827-399a-4ab7-8451-ae5854d9cc5a>

Royal Horticultural Society (RHS). 2026. *Updated guidance on box tree moth and integrated management options*. RHS Biodiversity Webpage Update: Box Tree Caterpillar. Available from: <https://www.rhs.org.uk/biodiversity/box-tree-caterpillar>. Planned 2026 website update.

3.2 Still planned (future) output / dissemination post project

3.2.1 Article(s) for publication in journals

Authors TBD, Simmons G, Bird S, Kenis M, Del Pozo A, Herz A, et al. 2027. Integrated pest management options for *Cydalima perspectalis*: synthesis of outcomes from Euphresco project 2021-C-382 '*Potential for using IPM tools to control or eradicate box tree moth incursion (BTM-IPM)*'. *In preparation*.

Bielski JT, Simmons GS, Baez I, Swank C, Del Pozo-Valdivia AI. 2026. Evaluation of insecticide treatments for regulatory management of the invasive defoliator *Cydalima perspectalis* in the U.S. In preparation.

Bird S, O'Neill L. 2026. UK status of box tree moth (*Cydalima perspectalis*) and its parasitoids: implications for integrated pest management in ornamental landscapes. *British Journal of Entomology and Natural History*. In preparation.

Bjeliš M, Armada AR, Daugherty M, Simmons G. 2026. Evaluation of mating disruption for control of box tree moth, *Cydalima perspectalis*, in urban areas within its invaded European range in Croatia. In preparation.

Bjeliš M, Armada AR, Simmons G. 2026. Evaluation of traps, pheromone lure dose, and female attractants for box tree moth detection. In preparation.

Cuasay E, Del Pozo A, Simmons GS, Baez I, Perry KI, Ward SF. 2026. Validating phenology models to optimize management of box tree moth in North America. In preparation.

Del Pozo A, Rivera D, Bielski B, Sisk E, Brindley J. 2026. Phenology of box tree moth in western New York, USA. In preparation.

Kenis M, Klipstein S, Lee M, Lee S, Hamelin S, Chapuis J, Seehausen ML. 2026. Parasitism of the adventive parasitoid *Eriborus* sp. on planted and wild box trees in Europe. Submitted, pending publication.

Seehausen ML et al. 2026. Biological traits of *Dolichogenidea* sp. (Hymenoptera: Braconidae), a potential classical biological control agent of *Cydalima perspectalis*. In preparation.

Seehausen ML et al. 2026. Biological traits of *Eriborus* sp. (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae), a potential classical biological control agent of *Cydalima perspectalis*. In preparation.

Seehausen ML et al. 2026. The parasitoid complex of *Cydalima perspectalis* in South Korea and their potential as classical biological control agents. In preparation.

Simmons G, Del Pozo A et al. 2026. Evaluation of area-wide control of box tree moth, *Cydalima perspectalis*, in urban areas of western New York State. In preparation.

3.2.2 Grey literature

Bird S, O'Neill L. 2026. Box tree moth in the UK—what gardeners need to know. *The Garden (Royal Horticultural Society)*. Planned popular-science article; to accompany update to the RHS Box Tree Caterpillar webpage (<https://www.rhs.org.uk/biodiversity/box-tree-caterpillar>). Forthcoming 2026.

Lee J, McDonald N, Dodge C. 2026. Box tree moth, a pretty but pernicious pest. *Digger Magazine: Growing Knowledge*. Trade publication by Oregon State University/USDA/Oregon Association of Nurseries. Publication date TBD.

3.2.3 Events

Events refers to conferences, technical meetings, lectures, etc.

Del-Pozo A. 2026. Box tree moth (BTM): status update from western New York. My Educational Programs / Sessions @ Cultivate. J. Owen. Virginia Beach (VA): The Lawn & Garden Marketing Association, My Trade Show. <https://www.showcasetexas.org/speaker-Alejandro-Del-Pozo.aspx>

Kenis DM. 2026 Aug 5. A biological plot twist: can an adventive parasitoid protect boxwood? AmericanHort. <https://americanhort.org/events/a-biological-plot-twist-can-an-adventive-parasitoid-protect-boxwood/>

3.2.4 Other Visibility actions

Radio / TV / social media posts / ...

Royal Horticultural Society (RHS). 2026. *Updated guidance on box tree moth and integrated management options*. RHS Box Tree Caterpillar public webpage update. Available from: <https://www.rhs.org.uk/biodiversity/box-tree-caterpillar>. *Planned 2026*.

4. Impact evaluation: self-assessment

4.1 Feedback on the alignment to the Euphresco objectives and Strategic Research Agenda

Now the project is finished, do you still agree that all general objectives and the scope of Euphresco were met:

- a) to better coordinate national and regional plant health research programmes;
X Yes No
- b) to provide better research support for policy and operations through transnational cooperation and collaboration (e.g. trans-national research projects) that optimises limited funds;
X Yes No
- c) The project met at least one objective of Euphresco' s Strategic Research Agenda
X Yes No

By the end of the project, there were still at least three partners (EUPHRESCO members?) from at least 2 different countries?

X Yes No

If appropriate, describe any important changes in the consortium composition and programme as compared to the project proposal.

During the project, the consortium expanded beyond the original proposal. Additional scientific and technical specialists from participating institutions became involved, and experts from other organizations also contributed informally. In total, contributors from 10 member countries and more than 40 scientists and technical specialists participated, strengthening made important contributions to the project to meet the core objectives.

4.2 Lessons learned and benefits from transnational cooperation/collaboration (1/2 page ca.)

The project benefited from international collaboration with partners from ten member countries and more than forty contributing scientists and technical specialists. This broad participation supported information exchange, method alignment, and comparison of approaches across different environments. The diversity of contributors helped ensure that the results were practical and relevant to both European and North American contexts and

All core partners contributed to the work packages, and the collaborative structure remained stable despite some personnel turnover at individual institutions. In those instances, member organizations supplied new scientific and technical staff so work could continue without major disruption. Only one original member country withdrew, and this did not significantly affect overall progress.

The project also helped build professional connections and new research projects that are ongoing and likely to continue. A planned follow-up activity includes preparing a review article summarizing integrated pest management options for *Cydalima perspectalis*, based on the findings of this Euphresco project.

4.3 Integrative and multidisciplinary approach

No activity to report

4.4 Impact on Plant Health and the economy

The project has generated information that is already supporting plant protection decision making. In the United States, results from consortium studies contributed to updated plant-protection standards for safeguarding boxwood nursery stock, an industry valued at more than \$140 million annually in North America.

Collaborative work among partners on foreign exploration and evaluation of potential biological control agents has accelerated efforts to identify and assess candidates for future release. This work is continuing as a direct follow-on to the project. In North America and Switzerland, scientists are gathering the data required to petition for release of suitable agents, while in Europe the adventive establishment of a new *Eriborus* sp. and its strong impacts on BTM populations are being documented. These developments may support longer-term IPM solutions and help protect natural and heritage boxwood stands.

Studies on mating disruption showed that it can reduce moth activity and damage under a range of conditions. These results may help guide decisions on registering new or additional semiochemical products in

BTM-affected countries, offering growers and land managers more options. Development, registration and marketing of a mating disruption products in North American markets may also provide tools to help slow the spread or conduct eradications in newly detected BTM populations. Overall, the collective outputs of the contributing members are expected to improve plant protection and support the economic stability of the boxwood industry in Europe and North America, while helping safeguard heritage plantings and natural boxwood forests.

4.4.1 Was a valorisation and implementation pathway identified?

Yes No

If yes, can you briefly describe? (max 5 lines)

If no, are there still plans to do so? (max 5 lines)

4.4.2 Was the research adopted either nationally (NPPO's of the consortium partners) or internationally (RPPO or other): was there any demonstrated support of national, regional or/ international policy through diagnostic protocols, PRAs, policy actions, technological innovations (new varieties, new methods...) or other valorisation pathways of the results?

Yes No

- Results from the project contributed to updated safeguarding guidance reflected in the Box Tree Moth (*Cydalima perspectalis*) Compliance Agreement, used in the United States to protect nursery stock during movement.
- Project findings also informed policy discussions in North America and Europe regarding biological control options and integrated management practices.
- Networking among member countries helped secure grant funding to support new and ongoing projects on biological control and other IPM control tactics.

4.4.3 Do you anticipate any of the above-mentioned impact in the future?

Yes No

- Ongoing work on potential biological control agents, initiated through this project, is expected to support future petitions for release in North America and help improve IPM management of BTM in Europe where *Eriborus* adventive established was documented during the course of this project.
- Additional impact is expected as mating-disruption results may support registration of new or expanded semiochemical products for BTM management

Annex I: Technical meeting agendas

First Semi-annual Euphresco BTM Research Update Meeting: Potential for using IPM tools to control or eradicate box tree moth (*Cydalima perspectalis*) incursions

Date : January 27, 2023
Time: 0600-10:00 UTC-8

6:00 – 6:05	<u>Introduction</u>	Greg Simmons
6:05 – 6:30	Brief Introductions of working group members, 1 minute each. Name, Institution, BTM research area	All Attendees
	<u>Biology and Ecology I</u>	
6:30 – 6:42	1) Phenology of box tree moth in Western New York, USA , Alejandro Del Pozo, Elidah Sisk and Julie Brindley	
6:42 – 6:54	2) Box tree moth mating behavior in the field and laboratory . Ana Romana Armanda, Mario Bjeliš and Greg Simmons	
6:54 – 7:06	3) Status of box tree moth and its natural enemies in the UK , Andrew Salisbury (on behalf Of Stephanie Bird) RHS, UK	
7:06 – 7:18	4) Assessing Flight Propensity of the Box Tree Moth, <i>Cydalima perspectalis</i> using Flight Mill Methodology Helena Virić, Gašparić, Katarina M. Mikac, Jose H. Dominguez Davila, Ivana Pajač Živković, Mario Bjeliš, Hrvoje Novak, Darija Lemic	
7:18 – 7:28	<u>BREAK (10 minutes)</u>	
	<u>Biology and Ecology II</u>	
7:28 – 7:40	5) Development of an artificial mass-rearing diet for box tree moth . Mauri Hickin and Hannah Nadel	
7:40 – 7:52	6) Update on BTM mitigation programs at the European Boxwood and Topiary Society (EBTS UK) . Chris Poole	
7:52– 8:04	7) Top-down mortality factors of BTM in the Great Lakes Area and potential for biocontrol using egg parasitoid <i>Trichogramma</i> wasps . Alex Rimmer	
	<u>Biological Control</u>	

8:04 – 8:16	8) Survey of natural enemies and isolation of entomopathogens from native populations of Boxwood moth <i>Cydalima perspectalis</i> in Northern Spain. Rosa Murillo, Iñigo Ruiz de Escudero.	
8:16 – 8:28	9) Classical biological control of the box tree moth using parasitoids from Asia. Lukas Seehausen, Ikju Park, Soohyun Kim, Ji-yun Kim, Eun Ji Lim, Fanny Deiss, and Marc Kenis	
	<u>Detection</u>	
8:28 – 8:40	10) Evaluation of traps, pheromone lure dose, and female attractants for box tree moth detection. Mario Bjeliš, Ana Romana Armanda, and Greg Simmons	
8:40 – 8:50	<u>BREAK (10 minutes)</u>	
	<u>IPM Control Technology</u>	
8:50 – 9:02	11) Host suitability and insecticide efficacy for box tree moth in southern Ontario. Abigail Wiesner, Hannah Fraser, Sandy M. Smith and Cynthia Scott-Dupree	
9:02 – 9:14	12) Evaluation of Insecticide Treatments for box tree moth control. Cristi L Palmer and Matt Havers	
9:14– 9:26	13) Evaluation of mating disruption for box tree moth area-wide control programs. Greg Simmons, Ana Romana and Mario Bjeliš	
9:26 – 9:38	14) Radiation Biology for Sterile Insect Technique. Hannah Nadel, Greg Simmons	
9:38– 9:55	Discussion	All Attendees
9:55 – 10:00	Closing Remarks/Next Meeting	Greg Simmons

Second Semi-annual Euphresco BTM Research Update Meeting: Potential for using IPM tools to control or eradicate box tree moth (*Cydalima perspectalis*) incursions.

Date : January 23, 2024, Time: 0600-10:00 UTC-8

Time	Topic	Presenter(s)	Duration (mins)
6:00-6:05	Welcome & Introduction	Greg Simmons	5
6:05-6:25	Brief Introductions of working group members, 1 minute each. Name, Institution, BTM research area	All	20
Biology, Ecology & Monitoring			
6:25-6:37	Progress on development of an artificial diet for box tree moth.	Mauri Hickin & Christine Swank	12
6:37-6:47	Estimating the effective sampling area of BTM traps, Part 1, Experimental methods.	Mario Bjeliš & Ana Romana Armanda	10
6:47-6:57	Estimating the effective sampling area of BTM traps, Part 2 modeling analysis.	Matt Daugherty	10
6:57-7:07	Genetic analysis of the invasive BTM population in North America	Yunke Wu	10
7:07-7:17	DISCUSSION		10
Biological Control			
7:17-7:29	Studying BTM parasitoids from South Korea for classical biological control.	Lukas Seehausen	12
7:29-7:39	BREAK		10
7:39-7:41	BTM biocontrol beginnings: collection, identification, and rearing of non-target moths	Chrissy Dodge	12
7:41-7:53	First record of <i>Nemorilla floralis</i> (Fallén, 1810) (Diptera, Tachinidae) parasitism on box tree moth.	Ana Romana Armanda	12
7:53-8:05	Surveillance of European <i>Cydalima perspectalis</i> parasitoids	Lindsey O'Neill & Stephanie Bird	12
8:05-8:17	DISCUSSION		10
Management & IPM			
8:17-8:29	Update on BTM mitigation programs at the European Boxwood and Topiary Society (EBTS UK).	Chris Poole	12
8:29-8:39	BREAK		10
8:39-8:51	Evaluation of the effect of plot size on the efficacy of mating disruption on box tree moth control.	Mario Bjeliš	12
8:51-9:03	Management of the box tree moth on <i>Buxus</i> natural formations in NW Italy.	Chiara Ferracini	
9:03-9:15	Area-wide control of box tree moth in urban areas in Western New York with mating disruption and Btk applications.	Greg Simmons	12
9:15-9:27	Screening Insecticides for regulatory treatment of the eggs and 1st instars of box tree moth.	Cristi Palmer & Matt Havers	12
9:27-9:39	Evaluation of adjuvants for BTM insecticide treatments.	Dan Gilrein	12
9:39-9:54	DISCUSSION & CLOSING REMARKS	ALL	15

Final Euphresco BTM-IPM Working Group Research Meeting: Potential for using IPM tools to control or eradicate box tree moth (*Cydalima perspectalis*) incursions.

Date : March 06, 2026, Time: 0600-10:00 UTC-8

Time	Topic	Presenter(s)	Duration(min)
6:00-6:05	Welcome & Introduction	Greg Simmons	5
6:05-6:25	Brief Introductions of working group members and guests, 1 minute each. Name, Institution, BTM research area	All	20
6:25-6:37	BTM diet-based rearing system development	Christine Swank & Mauri Hickin	12
	Biological Control		
6:37-6:49	Surveys for classical biological control agents of the box tree moth in South Korea, Japan, and China	Lukas Seehausen	12
6:49-7:01	Biological traits of <i>Eriborus</i> sp. (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae), a potential classical biological control agent of <i>Cydalima perspectalis</i>	Serena Gallizia	12
7:01-7:13	Evaluation of <i>Eriborus</i> sp. (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) as a candidate BTM biocontrol agent: progress and prospects	Angela Hoover	12
7:13-7:23	DISCUSSION		10
7:23-7:33	BREAK		10
7:33-7:45	Parasitism of the adventive parasitoid <i>Eriborus</i> sp. on planted and wild box trees in Europe".	Marc Kenis	12
7:45-7:57	Laboratory evaluation of the potential of <i>Exorista larvarum</i> (L.) as a biocontrol agent against the box tree moth <i>Cydalima perspectalis</i> (Walker)	Serena Gallizia	12
7:57-8:09	Exploring endogenous natural enemies and entomopathogens for sustainable management of the invasive Box Tree Moth (<i>Cydalima perspectalis</i>)	Rosa Murillo & Iñigo Ruiz de Escudero	12
8:09-8:19	DISCUSSION		10
	Ecology, Management & IPM		
8:19-8:31	Phenology of box tree moth: applying historical models to ongoing invasion dynamics	Sam Ward	12
8:31-8:43	Area-wide control of box tree moth in urban areas in Western New York with mating disruption and Btk applications.	Greg Simmons	12
8:43-8:53	BREAK		10
8:53-9:05	Case study on mating disruption to control the box tree moth, <i>Cydalima perspectalis</i> in the Royal Gardens of Herrenhausen Herz, A. (Hannover, Germany)	Lüdke, D., Brand, T., &	12
9:05-9:17	Evaluation of insecticide treatments for regulatory management of the invasive defoliator <i>Cydalima perspectalis</i> in the U.S.	Jason Bielski	12
9:17-9:29	Development of Bioactive Peptide-Based Control Method for Box Tree Moth	Man-Yeon Choi & Sonu Koirala	12

Annex 2. Abstracts and short reports

Work Package #2: Develop enhanced monitoring methods

Evaluation of traps, pheromone lure dose, and female attractants for box tree moth detection. WP-2

Mario Bjeliš¹, Ana Romana Armanda¹, and Greg Simmons²

¹University of Split, R. Boškovića 31, 21000 Split, Croatia, email: mbjelis@unist.hr

²USDA, APHIS, PPQ, S&T, PPQ-S&T California Station, 1636 E. Alisal Street, Salinas, CA 93905

Objective of experiments was to conduct field trials in urban areas of Split – Dalmatia County in Croatia to evaluate which trap and lure combinations are most effective for detection and delimitation purposes.

Lure evaluation study: Four different lure loading rates of the two-component lure in a 5 to 1 ratio were evaluated with the goal will be to determine which lure loading rate is the most sensitive for detection. Two experiments were set with two trap types: large plastic orange delta trap (TRACE) and green Unitrap (TRACE). During 2021. year, large plastic orange delta trap loaded with 1, 6, 9 or 10 mg pheromone lure were evaluated on three urban locations Sinj, Brnaze and Poljica). Results shows that even 6 and 10 mg attract more BTM male moths, still there was no statistically significant difference between 4 lure formulations. During 2022. year, Green Unitrap traps were loaded with 1, 3, 6 or 9 mg pheromone lure were evaluated on urban locations in the coastal area in municipalities of Trogir and Seget. The goal of this was to determine and optimize which lure loading rate is the most sensitive for detection. Lure efficacy study shows that 3 and 6 mg attract more BTM male moths when used with Green Unitrap.

Female experimental lure study: Four different lure treatments (TRE 2680, TRE 2681, TRE 2638 and TRE 2639) were assessed with Green Unitrap traps during 2022. Year in urban area of municipalities of Brnaze and Turjaci in inland area. Assessments of experimental female lure shows promising progress in development of female targeted trapping activities where all tested formulations attract BTM females (and some BTM males).

Trap type evaluation study: During 2021. Year, three trap types for BTM detection sensitivity all baited with 1 mg lure (TRACE) were assessed: Multi-trap (bucket type trap yellow top and white bottom), large plastic delta trap (orange colour) with removable inserts and paper disposal delta trap with three side sticky surfaces. Experiments were set up in 8 replications (3 replications at Seget site and 5 replications at Trogir site). Results of the three types of traps testing clearly shows that Multi trap is significantly most attractive trap type in BTM males captures. During 2022. Year, four trap types for BTM detection sensitivity all baited with 3 mg lure (TRACE) were assessed: Multi-trap (bucket type trap yellow top and white bottom), large plastic delta trap with openings cut into the sides with removable inserts, paper wing trap and green paper carton trap used for trapping of gypsy moth. Results of the 4 types of traps testing clearly shows that Multi trap (green-yellow top and white bottom) (bucket type) is significantly most attractive trap type in BTM males captures.

Conclusions: Overall results of the several lure evaluation study and trap type study shows that Unitrap trap types (Multi trap or Unitrap both fully green and yellow-white colour) are significantly most attractive

trap type in BTM males captures. Regarding amount of pheromone lure loads, the optimized rate varies between 3-6 mg per trap. Assessments of experimental female lure shows promising progress in development of female targeted trapping activities.

Estimating the effective sampling area of BTM traps, WP-2

Matt Daugherty, Mario Bjeliš, Ana Romana Armanda, Greg Simmons

ABSTRACT

Trapping studies were conducted in an area of Croatia where BTM is widespread to evaluate the effective sampling area of pheromone traps. The first set of trials used a “single-release, multi-trap” design to estimate recapture rates of groups of fluorescently labelled BTM males at distances between 50 and 500 m around a central release point. Across the multiple unique releases, approximately 34% of marked BTM were recaptured. Analyses showed significant and negative effects of trap distance; mean recapture rates per trap declined from approximately 12% at 50 to 100 m to less than 1% at distances of 300 m or more. A second set of trials used a “multi-release, single trap” design to estimate recapture rates of small groups of moths (4 to 8) released at distances between 10 and 100 m surrounding a central trap. Analysis showed significant and negative effects of distance on recapture rates, from upward of 30% at the nearest release points to less than 3% at the 100 m release point. The two sets of trials were combined, and the proportion of captures at different distances were analysed with a linear mixed-effects model, which provided a fairly good fit ($R^2=0.75$) and showed a significant and negative effect of distance. This model fit was back transformed and integrated to estimate an effective sampling area of approximately 5,200 m (0.52 ha) surrounding each trap. This result may be useful for guiding decisions about appropriate trap densities for BTM surveillance.

Box Tree Moth, *Cydalima perspectalis*, Trap Evaluation Study, Western New York, July 2024

Gregory Simmons¹, Mackenzie Wahl¹, Treya Gough¹, and Eugenia Garcia¹

¹Forest Pest Methods Laboratory Salinas Field Station, USDA APHIS PPQ S&T, Salinas, CA

The current recommended BTM detection trap in the U.S is a green unitrap baited with a 3 mg pheromone lure and set with a Dichlorvos (DDVP) kill strip, though this trap has some limitations. Firstly, unitraps are costly, and when set with liquid killing agents, collected samples can take longer to process compared to other alternatives. Additionally, unitraps of any color are not permitted by the US Fish and Wildlife Service in sensitive habitat areas to protect the endangered rusty patched bumble bee (*Bombus affinis*), from risk of bycatch. Lastly, future changes in insecticide regulations could lead to the restriction of the DDVP strip in some states. In 2021-2022, we conducted a series of field experiments in western New York to assess the efficacy of several iterations of BTM traps. We showed that the unitrap is more attractive than several other traps, though we found that a large plastic delta trap (LPD) is comparable. Given the limitations of the current standard for BTM trapping in select situations, the purpose of this study was to further evaluate unitrap alternatives with the addition of lures at field sites located in Western NY.

In 2024, we evaluated unitrap alternatives by comparing the standard green unitrap with DDVP kill strips to several other options including: a unitrap with a round sticky insert (instead of a kill strip) baited with two 3 mg

lures, green LPDs baited with either one, two, or three, 3 mg lures. Results from the 2024 field season show there was a trend for greater trap catch on LPDs baited with 6 mg total pheromone (two 3 mg lures) compared to the other traps, though this was not a significant difference. While we have previous data that shows the standard unitrap is the most attractive trap type for BTM, in this case there were not any measurable significant differences in trap catch. However, because there is a need for trapping alternatives in areas where the unitrap cannot be used, or where the use of DDVP is restricted, we recommend the use of the green LPD baited with two 3 mg lures as the next best option for BTM detection in these areas.

Trap Evaluation, Newfane 2024

Figure 1 Male BTM capture on five trap treatments in Newfane NY in 2024. Treatments: 1= Unitrap standard; 2 = Unitrap with no DPVM kill strip, sticky insert and two 3 mg lures; 3 = Green LPD with one 3 mg lure; 4= Green LPD with two 3 mg lures; 5 = Green LPD with three two mg lures. By Proc Genmod (SAS) there are no significant differences between treatments.

Work Package #3: Conduct studies to investigate biology, population ecology, and behaviour.

Validating phenology models to optimize management of box tree moth in North America

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¹Department of Entomology, The Ohio State University

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³United States Department of Agriculture Animal and Plant Health Inspection Service

Introduction

- Box tree moth (BTM), *Cydalima perspectalis* (Walker, 1859), is a non-native, highly destructive pest of boxwood trees (*Buxus* spp.)
- Native to eastern Asia, BTM was first detected in North America in August 2018 (Ontario, Canada) and later in New York State in 2021.
- Since detection in New York State, BTM has spread to nine US states including Ohio, causing significant defoliation and plant damage.
- Current management relies on timed applications of *Bacillus thuringiensis kurstaki* (Btk), which are only effective against susceptible larval stages (Cook et al. 2021).
- The seasonal phenology of BTM larvae across the US is poorly understood, preventing precise timing of Btk applications and thereby limiting control efficacy. Understanding when larvae break diapause helps growers and managers optimize Btk treatments.

Objective

Evaluate the accuracy of phenology models for predicting the timing of BTM life stages in North America.

Methods

Fig 1: Locations of field data used to validate phenology models: moths (Ohio) and larvae and moths (New York).

Model frameworks: The Suppo et al. (2020) model incorporates temperature and photoperiod effects and was initially calibrated using European BTM populations. A simple degree-day model was also used, which predicts adult flight once cumulative degree-days (DD, base = 8.38 °C) surpass 513 DD (Nacambo et al., 2014).

Fig. 2: Conceptual framework of models compared.

Results

Ohio Site:

Fig. 3: Adult phenology predictions (black line: Suppo et al. (2020) model; blue line: simple DD model) compared with observed adult trap captures (red bars) in 2024 at Loveland, OH.

New York Site:

Fig. 4: (a) Larval phenology predictions (black line: Suppo et al. (2020) model) compared with observed immature counts (red bars) in 2024 at Page Avenue (New York). (b) Adult phenology predictions (black line: Suppo et al. (2020) model; blue line: simple DD model) compared with observed adult trap captures (red bars) in 2024 at Page Avenue (New York).

Discussion

- Based on visual assessments, preliminary forecasts using the Suppo et al. (2020) model aligned well with observed trap data. There were, however, several days of larval and adult activity missed by the model.
- Observed adult emergence occurred shortly after 513 DD had been accumulated, supporting the use of this threshold for predicting onset of flight.
- Incongruities between observations and predictions could highlight uncaptured microclimatic, host plant, and/or diapause larval dynamics, which strongly influence early-season damage.

Future Directions

- Incorporate field data from other regions of North America to refine predictions of larval phenology, including early season activation and subsequent generations.
- Quantify and compare accuracy of models using standard metrics (e.g., concordance correlation coefficient, omission and commission rates).

Acknowledgements:

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Reference:
Cook, J. C., Gillingham, T., Turner, C. P., van Broekhoven, B., & Helling, R. (2021). Invasive region guidelines: *Cydalima perspectalis*, box tree moth. US Department of Agriculture Forest.
Nacambo, S., Southard, R. L., Wan, H., Li, H., Hays, T., Baez, I., ... & Kevan, M. (2024). Development characteristics of the box tree moth *Cydalima perspectalis* and its potential distribution in Europe. *Journal of Applied Entomology*, 22(6-7), 18-26.
Suppo, C., Baez, A., & Rabiboni, C. (2020). A temperature and photoperiod-driven model reveals complex temporal population dynamics of the invasive box tree moth in Europe. *bioRxiv*.

Assessing Flight Propensity of the Box Tree Moth, *Cydalima perspectalis* using Flight Mill Methodology, WP-3

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Abstract

Box tree moth (*Cydalima perspectalis*, Walker) is an invasive species present in Croatia since 2012 where causes great damage to plants of the genus *Buxus*. The pest spreads rapidly, has high reproductive potential and good adaptability. Its known natural dispersal velocity is up to 10 km per year. Understanding flight characteristics of insect pests is essential for designing effective strategies and programs for their management. The aim of this study was to assess flight propensity of *C. perspectalis* and to evaluate its invasive character using flight mill technology. *C. perspectalis* flew a maximum distance of 15.6 km (virgin females) and spent a maximum time in flight of 241 minutes (4 hours). The average speed of *C. perspectalis* ranged from 1.1 m/s to 1.6 m/s. Knowledge of *C. perspectalis* wing characteristics and flight performances are of great importance in assessing dispersal and provide important insights into migratory activities.

Keywords: box tree moth, wings, invasiveness, flight mill, dispersal

Final Report
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Estimating natural dispersal and impacts of mating disruption for the box tree moth, *Cydalima perspectalis* WP-3

Matt Daugherty

Period Covered: 7/1/2023-6/28/2024

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Objectives

1. Estimate BTM natural dispersal distances and effective sampling area of pheromone traps. This objective will be addressed with empirical studies conducted in conjunction with project partners at the University of Split, Croatia.
2. Analysis of mating disruption plot size on BTM suppression. This objective will be addressed with empirical studies conducted by project partners at the University of Split, Croatia. Activities will be limited to consultation on study design and analysis of results.

Milestones

With respect to Objective 1, working with collaborators at the University of Split, Croatia, a mark-release-recapture study was designed to estimate the “effective sampling area” of the preferred unitrap bucket trap, which may yield important parameter estimates required by monitoring simulation frameworks (e.g., TrapGrid) to evaluate different surveillance strategies. The study design is based on prior work by Turchin and colleagues (1996; Environ. Entomol. 25:582-588) related to the monitoring of a wood-boring pest of pine trees. Prior work employed a “single-release, multiple-trap” design to estimate trap effective sampling area over relatively large spatial scales. During the most recent project period, those results were supplemented by a pair of “multiple-release, single-trap” trials to estimate recapture rates over relatively small spatial scales. For each trial, small groups (4 to 8) of lab-reared moths were released at one of four distances from a single central trap: 10, 20, 50 or 100 m (Fig. 1). Six releases were made for each trial at each of the different distances, with individual releases occurring at different locations surrounding the central trap. A total of 40 insects were released at each distance, in each trial, with insect groups at each distance marked with different coloured fluorescent powders (Fig. 1). The trap was checked four times for at least three weeks after the first release began, all insects were collected, and the number of each colour was recorded. The first trial occurred between mid-July and mid-September, and the second between mid-September and mid-October

- Of the 320 total marked BTM released, 45 (14.1%) were recaptured across the two trials, approximately 19% in the first trial and 9% in the second. Recaptures were generally higher in the first trial, and remained fairly consistent over time, while cumulative recaptures tended to decline in the second trial (Fig 2)
- An analysis of BTM recaptures using a generalized linear model with binomial error showed a significant blocking effect of trial ($\chi^2=5.194$, $df=1$, $P=0.0227$) and significant effect of release distance ($\chi^2=8.191$, $df=1$, $P=0.0042$; Fig. 3). Again, recaptures were more common in the first

trial, but both trials showed similarly strong negative effects of release distance on recapture rate at the central trap. In both trials, just 1 of 40 insects (2.5%) released at 100 m were recaptured versus up to more than 30% at nearer release points (Fig. 3)

- Next, we combined data from the prior single-release, multiple trap and multiple-release, single trap trials to estimate the effective sampling area. The methods followed those of Turchin and colleagues. This involved calculating the mean proportion of insects recaptured per trap at each distance in each trial, then fitting linear models that included only an effect of distance. Proportion captured was square root transformed to meet test assumptions, and distance was log transformed. The resulting model produced a strong fit ($R^2=0.75$) and showed a significant and negative effect of distance on recaptures ($t_{54} = -12.75$, $P < 0.0001$). The results show a decline in mean recapture rate from nearly 25% at the shortest distances to less than 1% at distances more than 200 m (Fig. 4).
- This model fit was then used to estimate effective sampling area using the same approach as Turchin and colleagues. The results indicate traps have a change of attracting BTM to them in an approximate area of 0.52 ha (i.e. $\sim 5,200 \text{ m}^2$) surrounding the trap. This result may be useful for guiding decisions about appropriate trap densities for BTM surveillance.
- An additional set of multiple-release, single trap trials were conducted by project partners in Croatia over the summer of 2024. The intent of these trials was to supplement the data available of BTM recapture rates over short distances. Analysis of these additional results are pending.
- Activity related to Objective 2 included consulting on the design and analysis of proposed field studies of the effectiveness of mating disruption to be conducted in the coming season in an area of Croatia where BTM is widely established.
- Trials related to Objective 2 were conducted by project partners in Croatia over the Spring and Summer of 2024. Trials consisted of measurement of BTM abundance in plants of varying sizes that included pheromone dispensers at a set density in different plot sizes to capture the effective area of mating disruption impact. Analysis of those trials are pending.

Preliminary results

Figure 1. Overview of multiple-release, single-trap design layout. The black triangle represents the central trap, and colored points represent different release distances for groups of fluorescent-powder labelled BTM.

Figure 2. Cumulative recapture rates of released insects at different distances. Solid lines represent the first trial and dashed the second.

Figure 3. Number of insects recaptured (out of 40 total) at different release distances in two separate multi-release, single-trap trials.

Figure 4. Combined analysis of both single-release, multi-trap and multi-release, single trap of the relationship between proportion of insects recaptured at different distances on A) a transformed scale and B) untransformed scale. Dotted lines represent model fit.

Box tree moth mating behavior in the field and laboratory. WP-3

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BTM mating behavior experiments were conducted in i) semi field conditions and ii) in open field conditions. Fully developed larvae and pupas were collected in public areas and private gardens and were transferred into laboratory for development to adults (one pupae/cup). 1-2 days old virgin females were used for experiments.

Experiments in semi field conditions: Experiments on mating behavior in semi field conditions were conducted during May, July and August 2020. Year by using field cages with 10 males and 10 females per cage (30 x 30 x 30 cm) that were placed in field. Observation of mating behavior were conducted during period starting two hours before sunset till sunrise next morning. When couple mating is observed, same are collected in cup and mating duration is recorded. After mating is finished, adults were separate each from other and then male is taken out from the cup. Precise time of mating event was collected for each mating pair. Total of 48 pairs were observed for 3 generations. Results shows that BTM exhibits simple mating behavior. All 48 matings occurred during scotophase. When mating pairs starting with copula during late scotophase (one hour before morning twilight), it was observed that mating can be extend to morning twilight period by 3 pairs in spring generation and 3 pairs in autumn generation. Mating pairs remain in copula for a mean of 71,27 minutes: 89,3 min. for 1st generation; 70,5 min. for 2nd generation and 67,12 min. for 3rd generation.

Experiments in open field conditions: BTM mating behavior experiments in the open field were conducted during 2021 and 2022. following methodology described by Height et al. 2003. for assessment of mating behavior of *Cactoblastis cactorum* (Pyrilidae). Experiments were conducted during first and second flight in the coastal and inland area of Split – Dalmatia County. Methodology includes using of individual mating tables with 17,5 cm diameter of mating arena (1 virgin female per table) and communal tables (10 virgin females per table) with 61 cm diameter of mating arena. Patches of box plants were selected for placement of both individual and communal mating tables. Total of 26 individual tables and 11 communal tables were used for mating behavior data collection. Tables were placed on host and non-host plants. Experiments were conducted during peak of flight of wild adults and tables were placed in the field 1 hour before sunset. To be sure that males are present in the experimental area, males originate from the laboratory were released in the morning and during afternoon always around twice more than females number on a day of experiment. Females express calling their behavior only during evening twilight by elongation of the abdomen (not upward but just straight) and wing flapping. This behavior least around 30 – 35 minutes before sunset. There is no calling behavior during night and neither during morning twilight. Males were observed standing on the nearby box plants or non - host *Cupressus* trees (3-4 males) on a distance from 2-3 meters from the tables. Some males were seen flying around tables and above table during females calling period. During observation in period 2021-2022 after “calling period” no pairs were obtained mating. Method for assessment of mating behavior for *C. cactorum* did not show any results on BTM mating behavior in field experiments.

Work Package #4: Evaluate the application of mating disruption.

Case study on mating disruption to control the box tree moth, *Cydalima perspectalis* (Walker, 1859) (Lepidoptera: Crambidae), in the Royal Gardens of Herrenhausen (Hannover, Germany), WP-4

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European box tree, *Buxus sempervirens* L. (Buxaceae), is an important ornamental plant in European garden culture for centuries. The box tree moth (BTM), *Cydalima perspectalis* (Walker, 1859) (Lepidoptera: Crambidae) with origin in East Asia, was accidentally introduced to Europe in 2007, has since spread across the continent and became a serious pest of box tree. Larval feeding causes defoliation until loss of shrubs, evoking aesthetic but also ecologic and economic harms. In the Royal Gardens of Herrenhausen, one of the most distinguished European Baroque gardens, boxwood is a major element of garden design, forming 18 km of hedges in total. *Bacillus thuringiensis*-based plant protection products have proven to be highly effective in controlling BTM infestations in urban green spaces, however, their use is cost-intensive and requires precise scheduling and extensive monitoring. Pheromone-mediated mating disruption is a biocontrol method based on releasing the sex pheromone of the target species in order to impair the ability of males to locate females and thus to reduce reproduction. Mating disruption techniques could prove particularly suitable in large box tree plantings, however, there is virtually no experience of its use against BTM in Germany. Here we report results of field testing of a mating disruption system, conducted in the Herrenhausen Gardens in the year 2024. A microencapsulated formulation of 7% p/p (Z)-11-hexadecenal supplied in a pump system was applied to 2,700 m² box plantations. Thereafter, capture of males in pheromone monitoring traps was inhibited (100% “shutdown”) and occurrence of larvae as well as damage on the plants was significantly reduced compared to control areas in autumn 2024 and also in spring 2025, especially in isolated compartments of the garden. Results suggest to rely on mating disruption as an alternative or supportive control method of BTM in such highly valued boxwood gardens. However, the product is currently not available on the German market anymore.

Evaluation of mating disruption for box tree moth area-wide control programs. WP-4

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ABSTRACT

We report the results from two years of field testing in 2021 and 2022 of an experimental mating disruption (MD) product for possible use in an operational control program to eradicate or slow the spread of BTM in the United States. The product was developed by TRECE* based on their CideTraktm meso-dispenser system, a solid rubberized plastic dispenser based on the major pheromone component for BTM, Z11-16:Ald.

This product was tested in a 70-ha trial in Croatia in 2021 and 2022. The results of the first trial were promising showing 99% trap “shutdown” and BTM larval reductions by as much as 75% in treatment

compared to control plots. Year 2 results were similar to the trial in 2021, with high levels of reductions in moth capture on pheromone traps and reductions in BTM larval density in treatment plots compared to control plots. Dispensers placed at the rate of 50/ha and 80/ha achieved similarly high rates of trap shutdown which suggests that the lower rate of dispenser placement would be effective.

A field study of 4 experimental female lures identified two lure formulations that are highly attractive both female and male BTM in MD treated fields which will be useful for monitoring under conditions of mating disruption.

To learn how to make use of this product to control BTM in landscape gardens, there are several questions that need to be answered including: 1) From how far away do mated females travel and how will this influence using MD for BTM control in landscape garden treatments?; 2) What is the minimum effective MD treated plot size? ; 3) and from what distance from other BTM infested boxwood are treated areas isolated enough so that they are protected ?

In 2023, we are proposing to conduct an operational trial in Niagara County, NY to assess the potential for MD and Btk treatments as part of an area-wide suppression program. Distribution of BTM in Niagara County Phenology suggests discrete locations where we could set up an operational trial with MD as primary tool Adding the use of an MD tool will make the initiation of an effective BTM eradication and slow the spread strategy more feasible in the United States and will also be a valuable tool to protect boxwood nursery production.

Evaluation of Area-Wide Control of Box Tree Moth, *Cydalima perspectalis*, in Urban Areas of Western New York State

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From 2023-2024, USDA and Virginia Tech scientists conducted an area-wide BTM control trial in Western New York. Applications of mating disruption (MD) pheromone (BTM-MESO, Trece), and BtK were made on three BTM infested landscapes. The goal of the study was to demonstrate the potential for BTM control using an area-wide strategy. Positive results could allow the adoption of an area-wide control program for local eradications of newly detected BTM as part of a “slow the spread” program to limit movement across the U.S.

A total of 51 acres were treated with MD and BtK. In both years, we observed reductions in BTM life stages in treated plots compared with untreated areas (Fig. 1). There was a 100% decrease in adult moth captures, 92-100% decreases in larval infestations, and 76-100% reductions in box tree moth damage during the last two sampling dates.

Results suggest that BTM in newly infested residential and commercial landscapes could be locally suppressed or eradicated using an area-wide control strategy. While having an MD product available would be an important component to include in a BTM control or nursery protection program, the BTM-Meso MD product for BTM

control is not yet registered by EPA for use in the U.S. However, BTM is relatively easy to control with timely applications of Btk and several other insecticides. The most important factor is to make sure applications are made when BTM larvae are most susceptible, specifically as the overwintering larvae break diapause in the spring, and with applications timed to target early-stage larvae after peak flight periods.

It is not known how soon after a new detection that active control measures need to be applied to ensure a successful local eradication, but we estimate within the first two-three seasons after detection. We have observed that the BTM natural spread rate is relatively slow from infested areas which makes local eradication more likely. It is also unknown how long it would take to achieve eradication of this species if it were attempted. Experience from other moth eradication programs, and based on our treatments, a BTM eradication effort should plan on 3-4 years of making active treatments, followed by post control monitoring. Other factors that are important to consider include the size of the infested area and the distance or degree of isolation from nearby areas with boxwood.

Figure 1. Number of BTM per one-minute visual survey on boxwood in treatment & control areas in 2023 (L) & 2024 (R). In 2023, there was a reduction of BTM life stages by 95% to 99% on the last two sample dates but this was not significant. In 2024, there was a significant reduction of BTM life stages on the last 3 sample months by 92-100% ($X^2 = , 10.61$ d.f. = 1, $P < 0.001$).

Work Package #5: Develop efficient mass-rearing methods on artificial diet.

Finalizing A Diet-Based Rearing System for Box Tree Moth. WP-5

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The rearing group at the Forest Pest Methods Laboratory (FPML) has been providing support to the Box Tree Moth (BTM) program in federal and academic sectors since 2020. These BTM projects cover several areas of program interest including pesticide research, biocontrol applications, biology studies, detector dog training and sterile insect technique; this variety of projects requires BTM of all different life stages. Supporting a continuous BTM colony using host plant material is costly and space intensive, thus necessitating a more efficient method to rear large amounts of insects while maintaining a high standard of quality. An optimized BTM diet was developed to contain minimal host plant material. It was finalized using the JMP program, Design of Experiments. The diet uses 88% less plant material compared to traditional host-plant rearing. This diet produced insects of equal quality to the plant-reared colony in terms of quality control metrics, pupation percentage and pupal weight. The diet-reared BTM have a pupation percentage of 63%, and an average pupal weight of 0.2054g compared to plant-reared colony pupation percentage of 59% and average pupal weight of 0.1809g. Following the finalization of this diet, rearing protocols for diet-based rearing operations were established to streamline the production of both diet and insects. The development of a host-based BTM diet has streamlined rearing operations by decreasing the amount of money spent on plants by approximately 40%, thus saving ~\$2500 annually. Diet based rearing operations also utilize a much smaller space footprint than plant rearing (Figure 1), maximizing production capabilities. This has led to increased fulfillment opportunities for BTM projects supported by the rearing department at FPML. Protocols for the production of the BTM diet have been provided to collaborators.

Figure 1: Image of a rearing chamber containing shelves of cages for various life stages of BTM.

The cages used to rear plants are shown on the right and upper parts of the image. The same number of neonates can be reared in diet boxes noted on the bottom of the image highlighted by a white circle.

Section 508 Compliant Text: A large room containing several 3-tiered shelves lined with mesh cages containing BTM of various life stages. A portion of one of the shelves containing 10 small plastic boxes is circled with a green circle; a white text box accompanies the circle containing the text "500 neonates".

Development of an artificial diet that supports the full life cycle of box tree moth, *Cydalima perspectalis*

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A colony of box tree moth, BTM, *Cydalima perspectalis*, has been reared in containment at the Forest Pest Methods Laboratory since 2020 and is currently used for biological research, IPM studies, and biocontrol testing. Colony rearing methods rely heavily on host plant cuttings from *Buxus microphylla*, (cv. Winter gem), which are costly and difficult to source, especially in winter months. Store bought plants can also be treated with chemicals, resulting in poor colony health. Using plant material for rearing is time-consuming and variability in plant quality can cause unstable colony production output. While an artificial diet can be difficult to develop due to the host-specific feeding of larval BTM, incorporating one into the rearing system, has the potential to reduce time spent caring for plants and changing plant material in rearing cages. The goal of this work was to develop an artificial diet that supports the full lifecycle of BTM.

A total of 51 different diets were developed and tested from 2021-2022, and in 2023, a proprietary commercial diet was purchased (Insecta F2, Nihon Nosan Co. Ltd, Yokohama, Japan) that induced pupation. While this commercial diet showed that an artificial diet with added plant material could be developed, this diet was difficult to obtain, expensive, the proportion of ingredients was unknown, and larvae fed this diet had several pupal

deformities. Several in-house diet formulations were then tested that had a mixture of ingredients and ratios resembling the commercial diet, spongy moth diet and silkworm diet. From these trials, a new in-house artificial diet was developed at FPML that contained 30% boxwood leaf powder and supported the full life cycle of BTM. The larvae fed on the diet, developed at similar rates as larvae that fed on plant cuttings, and adults laid viable eggs. On average, the FPML in-house diet supported 66% pupation, which was marginally higher than the commercial-diet and plant cutting pupation rates (Figure 1A). In addition, the FPML diet-reared pupae were significantly heavier than pupae that developed on the commercial diet or plant cuttings during the same time period as the diet testing (Figure 1B).

Once the FPML in-house diet is fully optimized to reduce the amount of dried plant material, it can be incorporated into the rearing system. Insects reared on diet will be easier to maintain, and more synchronous in their development. As a result, more life stages will be available for biology research, IPM studies, and biocontrol testing. Future work will focus on optimizing the diet to produce consistently high-quality insects, and the development of methods to incorporate the optimized diet into the rearing system.

Figure 1. Average percent pupation (A) and average pupal weight (B) of BTM that fed on the commercial diet, FPML diet or plant cuttings. No significant differences in pupation rates were shown among larvae fed either diet or plant cuttings (One-way ANOVA $F = 2.1497$; $df = 2,36$; $P = 0.1312$). Average pupal weight was higher for larvae fed the FPML diet compared to the commercial diet and plant cuttings (One-way ANOVA $F = 13.7370$; $df = 2,125$; $P < 0.0001$). Groups that do not share letters are significantly different from each other (Tukey's honestly significant difference test, $p < 0.05$).

Current status of artificial diet development. WP-5

Christine Swank-Wells, Mauri Hickin

A lab colony of *Cydalima perspectalis*, box tree moth (BTM), at the USDA-APHIS-PPQ-S&T Forest Pest Methods Laboratory (FPML) in Buzzards Bay, MA has been successfully reared since 2020 on cuttings from *Buxus microphylla* cv 'Winter Gem'. Rearing BTM primarily on host plant material is costly and time intensive. Furthermore, the uncertainty of prior plant treatment can lead to plant material that has been treated with pesticides, thus severely limiting BTM rearing operations. Goals for FPML over the last several years have been to rear high quality BTM to support integrated pest management (IPM) research and to enhance rearing efficiency and reliability through the development of an artificial diet and diet-based rearing system. From 2022 – 2025, in addition to thousands of insects produced for colony maintenance, over 56,000 insects were produced to support pesticide studies, biocontrol research, biology research, outreach displays, virus testing, bioactive peptide research, sterile insect technique studies, detector dog training and artificial diet development. An artificial diet containing minimal host material capable of sustaining the full life cycle of box tree moth was developed in 2024; this diet was finalized and optimized in 2025. Diet making procedures have been streamlined to be easily transferable to other users. Some fecundity testing is still required in 2026, but the diet reared larvae are currently on their 8th generation. This diet uses 88% less plant material than traditional plant rearing; significantly reducing overhead cost of plants and reduce variability in plant quality while still producing high quality insects. In terms of colony statistics, the plant reared larvae have an average pupal weight of 0.1809g, and pupation percentage of 59%; the diet reared larvae have an average pupal weight of 0.2054g, and a pupation percentage of 63%.

Work Package #6: Investigate the potential for classical biological control of BTM.

The parasitoid complex of the box tree moth in Asia for a classical biological control program in North America. WP-6

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Background

The box tree moth (*Cydalima perspectalis*, BTM) is an invasive lepidopteran pest of East Asian origin that has rapidly expanded across Europe since its first detection in 2007 and has established populations in North America since 2018. The species feeds exclusively on *Buxus* spp. (boxwood), causing extensive ecological and economic damage. In Europe and Western Asia, widespread defoliation has led to the

removal of ornamental plantings and severe impacts on native boxwood forests (*Buxus sempervirens*). In North America, where boxwood represents a high-value ornamental plant (valued at approximately \$141 million annually across 44 U.S. states), the pest poses a significant threat. Additionally, endemic species such as *Buxus vahlii* in the Caribbean are at risk. Given the limitations of chemical control, classical biological control—based on the introduction of host-specific natural enemies from the pest’s native range—is considered a viable long-term management strategy.

The project aims to identify, collect, and evaluate parasitoids of BTM in its native range for potential use in classical biological control in North America. Initial efforts focus on field surveys in East Asia (South Korea, China, and Japan), followed by the establishment of laboratory colonies in CABI’s quarantine facility in Switzerland. Subsequent phases involve biological and host-specificity studies, with the most promising candidates transferred to U.S. quarantine facilities for regulatory evaluation.

Surveys for Natural Enemies

Extensive surveys conducted between 2022 and 2025 revealed substantial geographic variation in parasitoid diversity and abundance. South Korea emerged as the most promising region, with a rich parasitoid complex. Across multiple surveys, at least nine primary parasitoid species were recorded. Parasitism rates were often high, particularly in early larval instars, reaching up to 96% in some cases and averaging 41.6% in 2025. Dominant species included the ichneumonid *Eriborus* sp., the tachinid *Peribaea* sp., and the braconid *Braunsia hodorii*. For the first time, also an egg parasitoid was found to parasitize BTM in its native area: *Trichogramma chilonis*.

In contrast, surveys in China revealed a simpler parasitoid community, dominated by *Dolichogenidea* sp., while only a few other species were detected sporadically. Japanese surveys yielded very low parasitoid diversity, with only the generalist tachinid *Compsilura concinnata* recorded at low parasitism rates. These differences suggest possible regional variation in ecological interactions and even raise questions about the native status of BTM in Japan.

Laboratory-Based Studies of Key Parasitoids

Detailed laboratory studies in Switzerland focused on several candidate parasitoids to understand their life-history traits and suitability for biological control.

Eriborus sp. is a synovigenic solitary larval endoparasitoid and one of the most promising candidates. It parasitizes all larval instars of the BTM but shows highest developmental success in first to fifth instars. Development time at room temperature ranges from 26 to 37 days depending on the attacked host instar, and adult longevity averages 35 days. The species is mainly thelytokous (producing females without mating) and can overwinter within host larvae. First tests indicate high host specificity: while some related Crambidae species were occasionally attacked, no successful development occurred, suggesting a narrow host range.

Dolichogenidea sp. (Hymenoptera: Braconidae) is a gregarious larval endoparasitoid and the dominant species in China. It preferentially attacks early instars (1st–3rd) with high parasitism rates (71–92%). Development from egg to adult takes ~28 days, and females oviposit immediately after emergence without a pre-oviposition period. Preliminary host specificity tests showed successful development only on BTM, reinforcing its candidacy for biological control.

Braunsia hodorii (Hymenoptera: Braconidae), newly described in 2024, is another solitary larval endoparasitoid. It preferentially parasitizes early instars, with highest success in third instars. Development time is 29–57 days, and the species can overwinter successfully. However, laboratory rearing encountered challenges due to skewed sex ratios, limiting further experimentation.

Peribaea sp. (Diptera: Tachinidae) emerged as a dominant parasitoid in South Korea. Successful laboratory rearing was achieved in 2025, with parasitism rates exceeding 60% in some generations. Development time from parasitism to pupariation is approximately 15–16 days, with a generation time of

around 38 days. However, laboratory rearing remains an issue that so far limits further studies on this species.

Conclusions and Future Directions

The project has successfully identified a diverse parasitoid complex associated with BTM in its native range, with South Korea representing a key source of candidate species. Among these, *Eriborus* sp., *Dolichogenidea* sp., and *Peribaea* sp. show the greatest promise for classical biological control. Laboratory studies have provided essential data on their biology, rearing, and host specificity.

Future work will prioritize comprehensive host range testing, particularly with North American species, and the transfer of selected candidates to U.S. quarantine facilities. Given that host specificity is the primary criterion for regulatory approval, ongoing research aims to refine risk-benefit assessments and ensure safe implementation. The recent finding of the accidental establishment of *Eriborus* sp. in Switzerland and Germany provides a unique opportunity to study its field ecology and host specificity in regions where the BTM is invasive. Ultimately, the project represents a critical step toward sustainable, long-term management of BTM in invaded regions through classical biological control.

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Parasitism of the adventive parasitoid *Eriborus* sp. on planted and wild box trees in Europe, WP6

Marc Kenis, Seraina Klopstein, Minh Lee, Seunghwan Lee, Sandra Hamelin, Jules Chapuis, M. Lukas Seehausen

The box tree moth, *Cydalima perspectalis* (Lepidoptera: Crambidae) is not only a pest of ornamental box trees in Europe and North America. It is also seriously threatening the survival of European wild *Buxus* spp., and very few control options are currently available to save wild *Buxus* spp. stands. Surveys for parasitoids in the native range of the moth in South Korea showed that an undescribed species of *Eriborus* (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) is an important larval parasitoid of the box tree moth. This species is, among others, considered for classical biological control of the box tree moth in Europe and North America. However, it was also found for the first time in Europe in 2024 in Basel, Switzerland. In spring 2025, surveys were made to assess parasitism of box tree moth populations at various sites in North-Western Switzerland and at one site in South-Western Germany. These surveys showed that the parasitoid is well established in the region, both in gardens and in wild box tree stands. Morphological observations and molecular analyses showed that the specimens found in Switzerland and Germany belong to the same species as specimens collected on box tree moth in South Korea. Parasitism was highest in wild stands, reaching 68% in Germany and 32% in Switzerland. This parasitoid likely arrived unintentionally some years ago with the importation of box trees from East Asia. These first results were published in Kenis et al. (2025). Further, unpublished surveys were conducted in 2025 to assess parasitism in the second box tree moth generation, monitor the phenology of the parasitoid and assess its synchrony with that of the moth. These studies showed even higher parasitism than in the first generation -up to 100% in wild stands and 50% in gardens- and a wider distribution than expected.

Rearing under natural conditions showed that, in North-Western Switzerland, the parasitoid and its host have two generations per year and their phenologies are well synchronized. The parasitoid overwinters as a first instar larva in young host larvae, mostly in their 3rd instar. These observations provide hope for the survival of wild *Buxus* spp. and for the successful control of the pest on ornamental box trees. The ecological host range of *Eriborus* sp. will be studied in the field by collecting potential non-target hosts at the European sites where the parasitoid occurs in high numbers. The recovery of box trees at natural sites will be monitored, as well as the need for control in gardens following the establishment of the parasitoid.

Reference

Kenis, M., Klopstein, S., Lee, M., Lee, S. and Seehausen, M.L. (2025) Will an accidentally introduced parasitoid save European box trees? *CABI Agriculture and Bioscience* 6:1., 0081

Investigate the potential for classical biological control of BTM: Developing an *Eriborus* sp. for use as a potential biological control agent for BTM in North America. WP6.

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Toward the goal of developing classical (or importation) biological control methods for box tree moth (BTM), host specificity testing of *Eriborus* sp. was conducted at the USDA APHIS Forest Pest Methods Laboratory starting in 2024. *Eriborus* sp. is an ichneumonid endoparasitoid of BTM collected from its native range in South Korea. To date, we have exposed *Eriborus* sp. to 33 lepidopteran species across 16 families. From no-choice tests, while we observed low to moderate attack rates on species within Crambidae (21.57%), Pyralidae (4.44%), and Geometridae (5.71%), no parasitoid progeny was produced from any non-target species tested to date. Further, when given the choice between native species and BTM, *Eriborus* sp. shows a strong preference for BTM, selecting BTM larvae in 97.8% of replicates. Our results suggest that this parasitoid is highly host specific (Table 1), and no alternate hosts have been identified thus far. *Eriborus* sp. appears to be a strong candidate for biocontrol releases in the United States. Pending the testing of additional crambid and pyralid species in the 2026 field season, we will be preparing a release petition for *Eriborus* sp.

Table 1. Non-target species exposed to *Eriborus* sp. during host specificity testing. Asterix denote incomplete replicates.

Family	Species	Common name	Number of attacks
Drepanidae	<i>Drepana arcuata</i>	Arched hooktip	0
Erebidae	<i>Halysidota tessellaris</i>	Banded tussock moth	0
	<i>Haploa clymene</i>	Clymene moth	0
	<i>Hypena opulenta</i>	Ukrainian swallow-wort moth	0
Hesperiidae	<i>Polites peckius</i>	Peck's skipper	0
Lasiocampidae	<i>Malacosoma americanum</i>	Eastern tent caterpillar	0
Limacodidae	<i>Euclea delphinii</i>	Spiny oak slug	0
Noctuidae	<i>Panthea acronyctoides</i>	Black zigzag moth	0
	<i>Phlogophora periculosa</i>	Brown angle shades	0
Nolidae	<i>Meganola miniscula</i> *	Confused meganola	0
Notodontidae	<i>Nadata gibbosa</i>	Rough prominent	0
Nymphalidae	<i>Danaus plexippus</i>	Monarch	0
Papilionidae	<i>Papilio glaucus</i>	Eastern tiger swallowtail	0
Sphingidae	<i>Manduca sexta</i>	Tobacco hornworm	0
	<i>Sphinx gordius</i>	Apple sphinx	0
Tortricidae	<i>Lobesia botrana</i>	EGVM	0
Saturniidae	<i>Automeris io</i>	Io moth	0
	<i>Hayalophora cecropia</i>	Cecropia moth	0
	<i>Callosamia promethea</i>	Promethea moth	0
	<i>Anthraea polyphemus</i>	Polyphemus moth	0
	<i>Anisota senatoria</i>	Orange-tipped oakworm	0
	<i>Dryocampa rubicunda</i> *	Rosy maple moth	0
Geometridae	<i>Oxydia vesulia</i>	Spurge spanworm	0
	<i>Euchlaena obtusaria</i>	Obtuse euchlaena moth	1
	<i>Besma quercivoraria</i> *	Oak besma moth	1
Pyrilidae	<i>Galleria mellonella</i>	Greater wax moth	0
	<i>Plodia interpunctella</i>	Indian meal moth	1
	<i>Homoeosoma electella</i>	American sunflower moth	1
Crambidae	<i>Crambus praefectellus</i>	Common grass-veneer	0
	<i>Fissicrambus mutabilis</i>	Changeable grass-veneer	1
	<i>Urola nivalis</i>	Snowy urola moth	7
	<i>Lineodes integra</i> *	Tomato leafroller	4
	<i>Saucrobotys futilalis</i>	Dogbane saucrobotys moth	2

Additionally, chemical ecology tests were performed on *Eriborus* sp. wasps after observations that the wasps were attracted to host-produced frass during host range testing replicates. Wasps were singly

exposed to host-fed BTM frass and a blank control within a y-tube olfactometer and first and final zone (Treatment Arm, Control Arm, Midzone) selections were recorded after five-minute trials. While further testing is required, preliminary results strongly support *Eriborus* sp. wasps being attracted to host-fed frass. In addition to behavioural assays, we isolated several compounds of interest from fresh host-fed larval frass using GC-EAD and GC-MS methods. Wasps showed antennal responses to benzaldehyde, benzyl alcohol, beta-linalool, and the compound phenol 2-methoxy, also known as guaiacol. Guaiacol is a documented component of insect frass and is also reported as a potential repellent to BTM adults ovipositing on boxwood. Guaiacol may be useful in the development of push/pull management strategies to repel BTM from boxwood while simultaneously attracting natural enemies.

A secondary test examined the attractiveness of diet-fed BTM larval frass to *Eriborus* sp. wasps. We found that while wasps were more indecisive about final zone selection, they were still first attracted to diet-fed BTM frass which supports the notion that wasps reared with diet-fed BTM in mass-rearing efforts will still be able to locate their intended hosts (Figure 1). These results also help inform the suitability of diet-fed BTM larvae for building the *Eriborus* parasitoid colony and for laboratory studies on *Eriborus*, which could reduce spending on costly boxwood plants for colony rearing.

Figure 1. A comparison of *Eriborus* sp. behaviors in Y-tube olfactometers in the presence of host-fed BTM frass (left) and diet-fed BTM frass (right). Bars represent total zone (Treatment, Midzone, or Control) selections pooled across replicates and are grouped based on first and final choices.

Other findings:

1. We observed that BTM exposed to *Eriborus* sp. appeared to consume less boxwood than control specimens. We conducted an experiment in which we quantified the amount of frass produced by

parasitized larvae and control larvae that were not exposed to *Eriborus* sp. (n=24). It was determined that parasitized larvae produced much less frass than controls (Figure 2, control mean = 0.8376g, parasitized mean = 0.3081g, $p < 0.0001$). The implication here is that even if *Eriborus* sp. does not kill host larvae outright, it serves as an appetite suppressant and lessens the severity of larval BTM feeding on boxwood shrubs.

2. This species of *Eriborus* can produce males; from currently anecdotal observations, males are more often produced by females kept in isolation or low-density colonies.
3. *Eriborus* sp. is very long-lived compared to other parasitoids; female wasps have been kept alive at FPML for over 60 days, and most wasps exceed a lifespan of 30 days. However, wasp behaviors change as they age—at advanced ages, aberrant behaviors increase which may signal a decline in the capability to parasitize BTM successfully. We are completing a study on the effects of age on parasitism attack success and wasp capabilities by analyzing the time it takes wasps from specific age groups to complete successive attacks, as well as the ultimate outcome for parasitized larvae. Our adult wasp age brackets in this study include 0-2 days, 5-7 days, 10-12 days, 25-27 days, 30-32 days, 45-47 days, and 60-62 days. Early indications show a “pre-oviposition” learning curve in which wasps are less likely to parasitize successfully until 5-7 days old, and a gradual loss of fitness past 45-47 days old.

Work Package #7: Conduct natural enemy surveys and evaluate the impacts of native parasitoids, predators, and entomopathogens.

Top-down mortality factors of BTM in the Great Lakes Area and potential for biocontrol using egg parasitoid *Trichogramma* wasps. WP-7

Alex Rimmer, University of Toronto

The box tree moth (BTM) is an invasive pest of boxwood in Europe and North America with few known natural enemies in its introduced ranges. A life history study was conducted via field observations and collections to investigate the presence of natural enemies of boxwood larvae and pupae in a Toronto City Park in 2022. Pathology from microorganisms (e.g., fungal and bacterial pathogens) was observed in BTM larvae from both generations with mortality rates up to 15%. Specimens will be sent for genetic testing in order to confirm the presence of and to attempt identification of the pathogens. One species of ichneumonid pupal parasitoid was also observed attacking BTM pupae in the second generation, although parasitism rates were low (1%). In order to investigate the efficacy of commercially available *Trichogramma* spp. as potential biocontrol for BTM, laboratory bioassays were conducted. Four *Trichogramma* spp. were assayed (*T. minutum*, *T. platneri*, *T. brassicae*, and *T. ostrinae*). All four species were able to attack BTM eggs, with parasitism rates ranging from 8 – 46 %, with *T. ostrinae* having the highest parasitism rates. *Trichogramma ostrinae* also had the highest adult emergence rates of 34%.

Conduct natural enemy surveys and evaluate the impacts of native parasitoids, predators, and entomopathogens. WP-7.

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The number of alien species worldwide is increasing, mainly due to globalisation. A notable example is the Box Tree Moth (BTM), *Cydalima perspectalis* (Walker), native to East Asia and first detected in southwestern Germany in 2006, likely arriving through infested *Buxus* seedlings. After its initial report, BTM quickly spread to many European countries, including Italy, where it was first observed in 2010. Box trees are commonly used for hedges, borders, and botanical art, valued for their ecological versatility and suitability for topiary. Natural box tree populations can also be found in beech forests and along rocky slopes in the Alps, contributing to Habitat 5110, which consists of stable xerothermophilous formations with *Buxus sempervirens* on rock slopes, in accordance with the 92/43/EEC Habitats Directive. BTM is multivoltine in its native region, capable of producing up to five generations annually. In northern and central Europe, it typically exhibits a bivoltine cycle. Natural enemies of BTM are found in regions of China, Japan, and Korea. In Europe, some studies have examined predators and parasitoids of BTM, but few reports exist from Italy, Germany, and France. Control methods for ornamental box trees in Europe primarily include chemical and biological products such as *Bacillus thuringiensis* var. *kurstaki*

(*Btk*). Due to their effectiveness, *Btk* treatments are currently the most common strategy to control BTM populations.

Tools/diagnostics/methods developed:

The project contributed to the development and validation of various tools and methodologies: a control protocol based on *Btk*, optimized for early larval instars and timed with pest phenology; a monitoring system that combines pheromone traps and field surveys for accurate assessment of population dynamics and intervention timing; a risk assessment framework that integrates species phenology, voltinism, and host plant availability to evaluate potential impacts on non-target Lepidoptera; laboratory and field bioassays to assess larval susceptibility and treatment efficacy; standardized biodiversity monitoring protocols measuring abundance and species richness; and experimental methods to study BTM biology, including fecundity, phenology, and host plant interactions.

Validation and performance (metrics, accuracy, reliability):

The effectiveness of the proposed IPM tools was confirmed through multi-year field trials: *Btk* treatments resulted in over 90% larval mortality within 5 days under field conditions. Laboratory tests showed complete larval mortality within 96 hours. No significant differences were found between treated and control plots regarding Lepidoptera abundance, species richness, or the Shannon diversity index. The methodology demonstrated robustness across different sites and years, as validated by statistical analyses such as ANOVA and post hoc tests. Nonetheless, some limitations were identified: reduced effectiveness in later larval instars and sensitivity to environmental factors such as UV exposure and rainfall.

Data outputs (datasets, repositories):

The project produced several valuable datasets, such as:

- Multi-year time series of BTM population dynamics (2019–2021)
- Larval mortality data across different developmental stages
- Biodiversity data covering 45–49 Lepidoptera species in both treated and untreated sites
- Ecological indicators, including species richness, abundance, and Shannon diversity index

Conduct natural enemy surveys and evaluate the impacts of native parasitoids, predators, and entomopathogens, specifically the surveillance of European *Cydalima perspectalis* parasitoids. WP-7

Dr. Stephanie Bird, Royal Horticultural Society (RHS), Lindsey O'Neill, DEFRA

Box (*Buxus* spp.) is a very popular plant in the UK; in 2016 of a surveyed 1400 UK private garden owners 38% grew *B. sempervirens*. Box is a key feature of period historic gardens and is the dominant plant in some semi natural habitats, e.g. Box Hill and the Chilterns (Southern England). In 2006 *Cydalima*

perspectalis arrived in Europe and from then spread rapidly throughout the UK. For a detailed overview see Plant et al. 2019. In 2023 the cost per annum in England, where the majority of the *C. perspectalis* population resides, was estimated to be \$19.5 (€17.9, £15.4) million (Eschen et al., 2023).

It was conjectured that there would be no native natural enemies of *C. perspectalis*, in the UK, due to sequestering of toxic compounds by the larvae. However, generalist parasitoid species have already been found to be able to complete their life cycle on *C. perspectalis*; the Tachinid fly *Pseudoperichaeta nigrolineata* and the Pteromalid parasitoid wasp *Stenomalina communis*. These were not found through a structured survey approach but rather happenstance, this work sought to assess the presence of natural enemies through rearing *C. perspectalis* larvae and pupae collected as part of a survey.

In 2023 a total of 20 sites were visited across Southeast England including those with culturally important wild box areas, private and public gardens. Sampling took place in two phases covering the overwintering generation and subsequent summer generation. Sampling focussed on areas where *C. perspectalis* had been present the longest; including sites in Kent: Wye and Biddenden where *C. perspectalis* was recorded in 2007 and 2009, respectively.

Despite low overall rates of parasitism observed, below 1%, this work identified a third native UK natural enemy; the Ichneumonid parasitoid wasp *Pimpla rufipes* (in prep. 2026). *Eriborus* sp. were not found.

Parts of this work have been presented at the following conference:

Bird S, O'Neill L. UK status of Box Tree Moth (*C. perspectalis*) and its parasitoids. Oral session presented at: Classical biological control of arthropod pests: theoretical premise and practical challenges Symposium 3-2. ICE2024: XXVII International congress of Entomology; 2024 August 25–30; Kyoto, Japan.

We plan to publish this work in a peer reviewed journal, potentially the British Journal of Entomology and natural history. Our public facing box tree moth webpage will also be updated: <https://www.rhs.org.uk/biodiversity/box-tree-caterpillar> and we may follow this with a news/popular science item in our magazine (The Garden) which is received by our 500,000+ members.

Laboratory evaluation of the potential of *Exorista larvarum* (L.) as a biocontrol agent against the box tree moth *Cydalima perspectalis* (Walker). WP-7

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The Box Tree Moth (BTM), *Cydalima perspectalis* (Walker) (Lepidoptera: Crambidae), is an invasive pest native to Asia, first detected in Europe in 2006, likely introduced through infested *Buxus* seedlings. This species is a serious threat to the genus *Buxus*, causing declines in boxwood populations. In Italy, the boxwood is highly valued for ornamental purposes, and natural stands can be found in beech forests and on rocky Alpine slopes, contributing to the formation of EU Habitat 5110. Even though in its native range the parasitoid complex is more diverse, in Europe, only a few parasitoid species have been found to

attack BTM, at very low rates. In this context, the ability of *Exorista larvarum* (L.) (Diptera: Tachinidae) to parasitize BTM larvae has been investigated in laboratory conditions. A stock colony of *E. larvarum* was maintained in the laboratory of Entomology of the University of Bologna, using *Galleria mellonella* (L.) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) as factitious hosts. In no-choice experiments, field-collected BTM and laboratory-reared *G. mellonella* mature larvae were separately exposed to mated *E. larvarum* females. The larvae were considered as “accepted” when at least one parasitoid egg was detected on their integument, and as “suitable” when at least one puparium formed. The results on host acceptance and suitability indicated that *E. larvarum* may help limit BTM in a context of conservation biological control. Bioclimatic models, predicting the future distribution of this pest, indicate a rapid expansion across the entire European continent, with a significant impact in southern regions, leading to the loss of a highly valuable ecological habitat. Given these predictions, research on parasitism by native parasitoids (including *E. larvarum*) is vital for developing biocontrol strategies to mitigate the impact of this pest in natural habitats.

Exploring endogenous natural enemies and entomopathogens for sustainable management of the invasive Box Tree Moth (*Cydalima perspectalis*).WP-7

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Introduction

The box tree moth (BTM), *Cydalima perspectalis* (Walker), is an invasive pest (Lepidoptera, Crambidae) which has a high specificity for the genus *Buxus*, but a high adaptability to new areas of distribution. BTM larvae cause severe defoliation and can attack the bark, leading to plant drying to death and posing a serious threat to both ornamental and forestry boxwood. BTM has rapidly spread through European boxwood forest. In Spain BTM was first detected in 2013 and rapidly has spread across the north area including Navarra. The damage caused by this pest in the forests of Navarra Forest is occurring on an alarming scale and boxwood masses had not supported the pressure of the infestation and died (REFINA, 2023). The rapid expansion of this pest poses a serious threat to the boxwood forests of the Navarre Pyrenees, which are an integral part of many priority and ecologically important habitats of the region.

The use of insecticides on both ornamental and natural boxwood is restricted or completely banned due to their impact on beneficial organisms such as pollinators or endemic species in forested areas (European Academies Science Advisory Council). Due to the pressure of the infestation in recent years, *Bacillus thuringiensis* var. *kurstaki* (Btk) has been widely employed due to its effectiveness, even against large caterpillars, although multiple applications per generation are necessary for control. Biological control agents such as natural enemies and entomopathogens also have been tested, including egg parasitoids (Göttig and Herz, 2016), fungi (López et al., 2022), and Baculovirus (Oberemok et al, 2017). However, all of these control measures have had limited success in stopping the spread of BTM and need to be deeply investigate for implementation in pest management programs. In this study a survey of natural enemies (NE), including entomopathogens, were conducted in order to obtain native isolates with promising features as biological control agents against this pest.

TM monitoring and sampling. To investigate indigenous NE populations of the BTM that could be of interest for the development of biological control programs, surveys were conducted in boxwood forests suffering significant defoliation levels (80-90%) of the pre-Pyrenean valleys of Navarra (Spain) during 2021-2024. Sampling was conducted during BTM field outbreaks, monitored by pheromone traps, including both overwintering (April-May) and summer (August-September) generations. A total of 3,481 alive larvae and 45 dead larvae were collected from 47 locations. Larval samples were obtained in 47% of the sampling points

Identification of natural enemies. Natural Parasitism from BTM larvae or pupae was observed on 29 field-collected larvae from 10 different localities. All classified specimens were identified as *Compiler concinnata* Meigen (Diptera: Tachinidae) as previously reported (Murillo et al., 2023). Parasitoid larvae emerged from BTM pupae and formed their own pupa beside. After 7-8 days adult of the parasitoid emerged from the puparium (Murillo et al, 2024). *C. concinnata* is a polyphagous parasitoid affecting more than 200 species, which female injects a single egg into the host body. The parasitoid remains in the egg stage until the host pupates, then emerges from the host. Taken together, these are not desirable characteristics for *C. concinnata* to be developed as a biological control agent.

The prevalence of natural enemies increased over survey period. During 2021 and 2022 seasons, only parasitism was observed in the 1.13% and 1.04% of the samples, respectively. In 2023 season, the incidence of entomopathogens busted in. Out of 630 larvae collected in the 2023 summer sampling, the 6.3% developed entomopathogenic fungal infections and the 4.3% baculovirus infection. Also, parasitism also appeared in similar prevalence with a 2.1% of samples

Baculovirus (Bv) infections was registered in 27 BTM field-collected larvae from a single location (Artaiz (42°44'24.3"N 1°27'47.0"W). Those samples exhibited Bv symptoms at late instars (L5-L6) and developed a full infection including liquefaction of corpses. OB were found by smear test of corpses under microscopy, that confirmed polyhedrosis infection. Although baculovirus potential to control BTM larvae had been addressed in previous studies (Rose et al., 2013, Oberemok et al, 2027), this is the first time that a baculovirus was isolated from *C. perspectalis* samples.

Entomopathogenic fungi (EF) were identified in 40 field-collected samples. In these cases, we observed mycelium developed on the corpses. This mycelium was used for inoculation of PDA (Potato Dextrose Agar) plates for identification. Entomopathogenic fungi were also isolated from *C. perspectalis* populations, with a prevalence of 4.3%, highlighting their potential as promising pathogens for further characterization and evaluation in pest management strategies. *Beauveria bassiana* has recently been reported infecting *C. perspectalis* larvae with high prevalence in boxwood forests in northeastern Spain (López et al., 2022).

Genotypic structure of Bv population. A total of 159 baculovirus isolates were obtained and identified as closely related to *Alphabaculovirus aucalifornicae* (AcMNPV). Among field-collected larvae (F0) and laboratory-reared BTM colony (F1-F5) 3 different genotypic variants were identified (Cype-A, Cype-B and Cype-C) by restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP). Profiles showing mixtures between these single variants were also occasionally found (Goicoechea et al, 2024). Cype-C presented an identical banding pattern to AnfaMNPV (Chen et al., 1996). Cype-A and Cype-B profile showed common bands to AcMNPV, despite characteristic fragments were distinguished for each variant.

Prevalence of covert infections in insect lines and viral load in adults. After observing evidence of Bvs reactivation on mature larvae from laboratory colony of *C. perspectalis*, qPCR analysis of adult (F0 to F5) confirmed vertical transmission. Viral prevalence (qPCR+) ranged from 100 % (F5) to 40% (F2). Similar viral load means were estimated across generations and ranged from 18.98 ± 11.54 to 4.92 ± 0.98 viral genome copies/ng DNA (Kruskal-Wallis test: $p = 0.74$) (Goicoechea et al, 2024). These findings confirm the ability of Bv to be transmitted transgenerationally, supporting its potential for the development of inoculative release strategies. Among the three predominant genotypic variants identified within the viral population, Cype-B was consistently transmitted across up to five host generations, making it the most promising candidate for further evaluation under field conditions

First record of *Nemorilla floralis* (Fallén, 1810) (Diptera, Tachinidae) parasitism on box tree moth *Cydalima perspectalis* (Walker 1859) (Lepidoptera, Crambidae) larvae. WP-7

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ABSTRACT

Box tree moth, *Cydalima perspectalis* is native to East Asia where it occurs on *Buxus* trees. Its natural distribution includes China, Japan, Korea and India, and it was accidentally introduced into Europe, Middle East, North America and north Africa through the trade in *Buxus* spp., where it can cause considerable damage. In the native range of *C. perspectalis*, three tachinids (Diptera, Tachinidae) are known to parasitize larvae of *C. perspectalis*, including *Exorista* sp., *Pseudoperichaeta nigrolineata* (Walker 1853) and *Compsilura concinnata* (Meigen 1824). Data on tachinid parasitoids parasitizing *C. perspectalis* on the European continent include only *P. nigrolineata*. Field collection of mature larvae and pupae of *C. perspectalis* during July 2020 in four locations in Split – Dalmatia County in Croatia resulted in collection of live tachinid larvae that were reared to adults. The tachinid specimens were identified at the Natural History Museum, London, UK, as *Nemorilla floralis* (Fallén, 1810) (Diptera, Tachinidae). Conservatively, 1.2 – 2.4 % parasitism rate was achieved. This is the first world record of *N. floralis* parasitism on *C. perspectalis* larvae, which can be added as a potential tool for *C. perspectalis* biological control.

Work Packages #8 & 9: Investigate control treatments with Btk, baculoviruses and chemical pesticide treatments. & Develop regulatory treatments, systems approaches and BTM phytosanitary measures to safeguard shipments of nursery stock.

Host suitability and insecticide efficacy for box tree moth in southern Ontario WP-8

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ABSTRACT: Native to Asia, box tree moth (BTM) (*Cydalima perspectalis*) (Walker, 1859) is an invasive pest first confirmed in Ontario in 2018. Determining the potential use of alternate host species besides

boxwood (*Buxus* spp.) by BTM and the efficacy of insecticides and biopesticides for BTM control were top priorities for development of an integrated management program. In the invaded range of BTM, there is negligible data available on the suitability of *Euonymus* hosts in terms of successful reproduction of the insect pest. Using choice and no-choice feeding experiments, the alternate host suitability of two *Euonymus* species, *E. alatus* and *E. fortunei* were examined using BTM larvae. Although feeding attempts were made on each *Euonymus* spp., boxwood was consumed 15 times more, confirming its superior palatability. Additionally, after 40 days, BTM larvae only survived and progressed to pupation on boxwood. The efficacy of three insecticides (chlorantraniliprole, deltamethrin, and abamectin) and two biopesticides (*Bacillus thuringiensis*, var. *kurstaki* and spinosad) currently used within the ornamental industry, were evaluated by determining their contact and oral toxicity to BTM larvae in the laboratory. Each pesticide was tested at its Canadian label rate. Following the contact bioassay, chlorantraniliprole provided the most effective control while abamectin provided the most effective control following the oral bioassay. A semi field trial using *Bacillus thuringiensis*, var. *kurstaki*, chlorantraniliprole, and abamectin at Canadian label rate demonstrated lower mortality rates but highlighted the potential of the chemical products and the importance of application method. Confirming boxwood as the primary host for BTM development and survival as well as demonstrating the efficacy of novel insecticides for BTM control is crucial for the Ontario nursery and landscape industry, influencing phytosanitary protocols as well as trade agreements.

Development of Bioactive Peptide-Based Control Method for Box Tree Moth WP-8

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ABSTRACT

Insect neuropeptides (NPs) and their G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs) regulate essential physiological processes and are promising targets for next-generation insecticides. Selective disruption of these interactions offers a pathway to innovative pest management strategies. We recently developed Receptor interference (Receptor-i) technology, a rapid discovery platform that screens short bioactive peptides using phage-display libraries and an insect cell-based GPCR expression system. We initiated to discover bioactive peptides using Receptor-i targeting box tree moth (BTM), providing a foundation for the development of novel peptide-based biopesticides.

Widening the toolbox: In-field insecticide efficacy and residuality for the new invasive Box Tree Moth in the U.S. WP-8 & 9

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Abstract: The invasive box tree moth (*Cydalima perspectalis*, Lepidoptera: Crambidae, BTM) poses a growing threat to North American horticulture, endangering the \$141 million U.S. boxwood industry. This study evaluated the efficacy and residual activity of six insecticides (Neonicotinoids: Dinotefuran (4a); Spinosyns + Sulfoximines: Spinetoram + Sulfoxaflor (5 +4c); Tolfenpyrad (21a); Diamides (28): Chlorantraniliprole, Cyantraniliprole; Diamides + Flonicamid (28 + 29): Cyclaniliprole + Flonicamid.) against box tree moth larvae in a nursery-like field setting. We were particularly interested in determining whether insecticides currently used for lepidopteran pests are effective against box tree moth and understanding their residual activity. Treatments were applied to 3-gallon *Buxus microphylla* ‘Winter Gem’ plants, and larvae were infested onto treated plants at intervals up to 49 days post-treatment. In-field survival assessments provided critical insights into effective chemical options against this invasive pest. Results highlighted the strong efficacy and extended residual activity of diamide insecticides, up to 49 days post-treatment, with treatment efficacy reaching up to 89.5% and 75.0%, respectively, when applied as foliar sprays or drenches, suggesting their potential as regulatory treatments. These findings provide vital guidance for protecting the boxwood industry from this invasive threat by informing quarantine management strategies and shaping treatment requirements under compliance agreements.

Table Below. Percent control of foliar and soil drenches 7, 21, 35, and 49 days after application on BTM larvae (instars 2–6). The statistical analysis assessed the proportion of BTM controlled (dead + sick + missing larvae) using a generalized linear mixed model with a beta distribution and a logit link function. The model included Treatment and Days After Treatment (DAT) as fixed effects, with Replication and Replicate-ID as random effects, accounting for variability across replicates. The study was repeated twice, with four replicates per treatment. Both repetitions were pooled, and the results were converted to percent. Residual diagnostics ensured model assumptions were met, and post hoc pairwise comparisons were conducted using estimated marginal means.

Active	Rate per 100 gal	7 days percent control	21 days percent control	35 days percent control	49 days percent control
Dinotefuran (Safari 20 SG, 20.0% active, EPA Reg. # 86203-11-59639)	0.5 lb (foliar)	49.4 ± 14.6 ab	45.8 ± 13.3 abc	31.3 ± 9.6 a	18.8 ± 10.6 a
Dinotefuran (Safari 20 SG, 20.0% active, EPA Reg. # 86203-11-59639)	0.5 lb (drench)	55.6 ± 11.6 ab	52.1 ± 14.3 abcd	79.5 ± 11.2 bc	52.1 ± 17.1 abc
Chlorantraniliprole (Acelepryn, 18.4% active, EPA Reg. # 100-1489)	16 fl oz (foliar)	94.9 ± 3.3 b	96.8 ± 3.1 d	97.7 ± 1.5 c	89.5 ± 7.0 c
Chlorantraniliprole (Acelepryn, 18.4% active, EPA Reg. # 100-1489)	16 fl oz (drench)	70.6 ± 8.19 ab	62.5 ± 10.7 bcd	64.0 ± 13.9 bc	75.0 ± 13.3 bc
Cyantraniliprole	16 fl oz	93.3 ± 3.9 b	96.8 ± 3.1 d	77.8 ± 7.7 bc	75.0 ± 12.6 bc

(Mainspring GNL, 18.66% active, EPA Reg. # 100-1543)	(foliar)				
Cyantraniliprole (Mainspring GNL, 18.66% active, EPA Reg. # 100-1543)	12 fl oz (drench)	60.9 ± 8.8 ab	70.4 ± 9.4 bcd	60.8 ± 11.5 bc	50.9 ± 8.9 abc
Cyantraniliprole + Flonicamid (Pradia, 4.46% + 5.96% active, EPA Reg. # 71512-33-59807)	17.5 fl oz (foliar)	99.9 ± 0.0 b	86.4 ± 6.3 cd	74.4 ± 9.2 bc	39.6 ± 16.0 ab
Tolfenpyrad (Hachi-Hachi SC, 15.0% active, EPA Reg. # 71711-36-67690)	27 fl oz (foliar)	61.3 ± 13.4 ab	36.3 ± 13.3 ab	70.4 ± 7.4 bc	39.6 ± 11.3 ab
Spinetoram + Sulfoxaflor (XXpire, 20.0% + 20.0% active, EPA Reg. # 62719-676)	2.75 oz (foliar)	99.3 ± 0.6 b	62.5 ± 8.3 bcd	61.1 ± 10.2 bc	31.3 ± 12.8 a
Untreated Control (UTC)	N/A	40.0 ± 10.8 a	23.0 ± 10.8 a	31.7 ± 7.9 ab	33.8 ± 11.7 a

Screening Insecticides for Regulatory Treatment of the Eggs and 1st Instars of BTM, WP-9

Cristi Palmer & Matt Havers IR4 Rutgers University, NJ.

Abstract

Seven on market insecticides and one propriety insecticide in the experimental phase were tested for efficacy using amended growth media during 2021-2022. Late-stage eggs were introduced to the media right before hatching and counts taken after 5 days (120 hrs.) after, which is the approximate developmental time for 1st instar larvae. In this experiment low label rates were considered the high label rate (x), with the three other experimental groups being x/2, x/4, and x/8, respectively. A control group of unamended media was included in each run. The results indicated that egg mortality was generally low among all actives except for carbaryl; where mortality ranged from 42% - 61%. For 1st instar larvae, all rates of tolfenpyrad, spinosad, carbaryl, and pyrethrin were highly effective with mortalities exceeding 95%. Mortalities within larvae exposed to fenpropathrin, dinotefuran, and cyantraniliprole showed variable efficacy; however, the high rates (low label rates) of these actives exhibited mortalities of > 87%.

Efficacy trials of 8 on market insecticides using foliar sprayed individual cuttings were completed in 2023. In this experiment eggs laid on boxwood cuttings were sprayed, and counts taken 7 days (168 hrs.) after the initial treatment. The high and low recommended label rates were used for this experiment. When only one label rate was given, that rate was considered as the high rate, with the low rate being half of the recommended label rate. Each replicated run contained both a negative control (water) and a positive control (spinosad) applied at the high label rate. Both rates of acetamiprid and the high rate of dinotefuran recorded the most egg deaths (> 80%); while larval mortalities among rates of acetamiprid, cyantraniliprole, dinotefuran, spinosad, and tolfenpyrad exceeded 90% mortality.

Screening Insecticides for the Suppression and Management of Eggs and Early Instars of *Cydalima perspectalis*. WP-8 & 9

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In 2021-2025, an efficacy study followed by two conceptual replications were conducted as a collaboration between Rutgers University and the USDA APHIS Forrest Pest Methods Laboratory in Cape Cod, MA to screen insecticides against the eggs and early instars of BTM. The three studies utilized eggs approximately ≤ 24 hours before hatch (referred to as “blackheads” to the beginning of 3rd instars. Insecticides screened were products available to growers and nurseries and were divided into two modes of action, nervous system disruption, and developmental disruption (Table 1). Two outreach publications were also produced- a visual guide and fact sheet published in 2022 (Frank et al. 2022) and insecticide options for BTM (Frank et al. 2023); the latter a compilation of previous and concurring management studies). In 2025 results of the 3rd study were published in the journal *Arthropod Management Tests* (Havers et al. 2025). Presentations of results were presented at applicable meetings throughout the length of the project, along with a presentation in a 2025 BTM symposium at the regional Entomological Society of America Annual Conference located in Little Rock, Arkansas.

The first experiment implemented lepidopteran rearing media amended with 4 rates each carbaryl, fenpropathrin, pyrethrin, dinotefuran, spinosad, tolfenpyrad, and cyantraniliprole. Control rearing media was amended with water. Females laid fertilized eggs on wax paper. The wax paper was cut around the periphery of the egg masses and was placed on to the rearing media. Approximately 10 eggs per rearing cell were used. Counts were taken 120 hours after infestation (Table 2).

The second experiment implemented boxwood cuttings of the variety ‘winter gem’ (*Buxus microphylla var. japonica*) with the high and low label rates of eight insecticides (Table 1). Mating pairs were introduced to cuttings, and 10 eggs were kept for each cutting. The cuttings were then promptly sprayed with the appropriate product and rate. Control cuttings were sprayed with water only. Counts were taken 168hrs after applications (Table 3).

The third experiment measured efficacy over time of 5 actives (Table 1) 0, 1, 2, and 3 weeks after treatment (WAT). 2-gallon pots of *Buxus microphylla var. japonica* were sprayed with 8 fl oz. of solution with a 2-gallon pump sprayer. Three cuttings would be removed from a plant and placed in a jar and infested with approximately 10 1st instar BTM larvae. Counts were taken at 72 hours and 168 hours (table 4).

Carbaryl showed the highest efficacy against eggs in the rearing media experiment. Acetamiprid performed well against eggs and larvae in the cuttings experiment, as well at 0 & 1 of treated whole plants. Fenpropathrin reported higher efficacy than pyrethrin in the rearing media and cuttings experiment. Bifenthrin was highly efficacious 0 WAT in the aged residue study. Spinosad was highly effective across all 3 experiments but quickly lost effectiveness 1 WAT in the aged foliar experiment. While all actives performed well 0 WAT in the foliar experiment, the high rate of chlorantraniliprole remained effective for 3 WAT. There generally was higher mortality in

the rearing media experiment than the other two experiments. “Nervous system disruptors” were generally more efficacious than “developmental disruptors”.

Table 1: Insecticide List

Formulation	Active	IRAC	Mode of Action
Sevin XLR *	Carbaryl	1A	Nervous System Disruption
Danitol 2.4 EC *†	Fenpropathrin	3A	
Talstar !	Bifenthrin		
Pyganic Specialty *	Pyrethrin	4A	
Tristar 8.5 †!	Acetamiprid		
Safari 20SG *†	Dinotefuran		
Conserve SC *†!	Spinosad	5	
Intrepid 2F †	Methoxyfenozide	18	Developmental Disruption
Hachi-Hachi SC *†!	Tolfenpyrad	21A	Nervous System Disruption
Mainspring GNL *†	Cyantraniliprole	28	
Acelepryn !	Chlorantraniliprole		
Aza-Direct †	Azadirachtin	UN	Developmental Disruption

* Rearing Media Study † Cuttings Study ! Aged Residue Study

Table 2: Efficacy/survivorship of 1st year rearing media study. * Indicates statistical significance from the associated control means.

Formulation	Active	Rate (fl oz/100gal)	Infestation (0hr)	Hatch (24-48 hr.)	Final Evaluation (120 hr.)
Control	Water	NA	10	8.5	8.1
Sevin XLR	Carbaryl	2	10	4.2*	0*
		4	10	4*	0*
		8	10	3.9*	0*
		16	10	5.5*	0.2*
Danitol 2.4 EC	Fenpropathrin	2	10	8.4	5.36
		4	10	8.5	3.75*
		8	10	8.5	3.74*
		16	10	8.5	0.94*
Pyganic Specialty	Pyrethrin	2	10	8.5	0.1*
		4	10	6.6*	0.2*
		8	10	7.8	0*
		16	10	8.8	0*
Safari 20SG	Dinotefuran	0.5	10	7.5	3.38*
		1	10	7.2	3.1*
		2	10	8.2	4.6*
		4	10	8.7	1.1*
Mainspring GNL	Cyantraniliprole	0.25	10	8.3	2.74*
		0.5	10	8	1.76*
		1	10	8.3	1.9*
		2	10	8.9	1.16*
Conserve SC	Spinosad	0.75	10	8.4	0.42*
		1.5	10	9.2	0*
		3	10	9.2	0.1*
		6	10	8.7	0*
Hachi-Hachi SC	Tolfenpyrad	1.75	10	8.6	0.1*
		3.5	10	8.7	0*
		7	10	7.6	0.22*
		14	10	7.2	0*

Table 3: Efficacy/survivorship of 2nd year cuttings study. * Indicates statistical significance from the associated control means.

Formulation	Active	Rate (fl oz/100gal)	Infestation (0hr)	Hatch (24-48 hr.)	Final Evaluation (168hr)
Control	Water	NA	10	9.5	9
Danitol 2.4 EC	Fenpropathrin	16	10	7.7*	2.16*
		21.3	10	6.8*	1.29*
Pyganic Specialty	Pyrethrin	16	10	8.7	5.31*
		32	10	8.1	5.18*
Tristar 8.5	Acetamiprid	8.5	10	1.5*	0.14*
		16.5	10	1*	0.21*
Safari 20SG	Dinotefuran	4	10	4.3*	0.26*
		8	10	1.9*	0.5*
Conserve SC	Spinosad	8	10	8.9	0.6*
Intrepid 2F	Methoxyfenozide	4	10	8.8	1.67*
		16	10	8.7	2.18*
Hachi-Hachi SC	Tolfenpyrad	21	10	8.2*	0.57*
		32	10	5.3*	1.1*
Mainspring GNL	Cyantraniliprole	8	10	7.2*	0.65*
		12	10	8.3*	0.5*
Aza-Direct	Azadirachtin	16	10	9.3	8
		32	10	9.1	9

Table 4: Efficacy/survivorship of 3rd year aged residue study. * Indicates statistical significance from the associated control mean.

Formulation	Active	Rate (fl oz/100gal)	WAT	Infestation (0hr)	168hr Evaluation	172hr Evaluation
Tristar 8.5	Acetamiprid	16.5	0	9.7	0*	0*
			1	8.6	4.4*	1.8*
			2	9.8	5.7*	5.1*
		8.5	3	9.4	7.2*	5.8*
			0	9.6	0.3*	0.3*
			1	8.1	2.7*	1.9*
Acelepryn	Chlorantraniliprole	16	2	9.1	7.0	6.8
			3	9	6.8	5.5*
			0	9.5	0.3*	0.1*
		2	1	9.7	0.5*	0.4*
			2	9.9	0.1*	0*
			3	9.6	0*	0*
Talstar	Bifenthrin	10.8	0	9.8	4.6*	4*
			1	9.4	1.3*	0.1*
			2	8.8	0.4*	0.4*
		5.4	3	9	3*	2.8*
			0	9.2	0*	0*
			1	9.1	6.7	2.6*
Hachi-Hachi SC	Tolfenpyrad	32	2	9.7	8.2	6.6*
			3	9.6	8.1	8
			0	8.8	0.4*	0*
		21	1	8.5	5.2*	3.5*
			2	9.6	7.8	7.8
			3	10	8.8	8.8
Conserve SC	Spinosad	22	0	8.5	1.6*	1.6*
			1	9.9	8.4	8.4
			2	9.6	8	7.6*
		NA	3	9.7	8.1	8.1
			0	9	4.8*	3.7*
			1	9.3	8.3	7.2
Control	Water	NA	2	9.8	8.6	8.5
			3	9.7	8.1	8.1
			0	9.5	0*	0*
			1	8.9	7.6	6.8*
Control	Water	NA	2	9.3	7.5*	6.3*
			3	9.3	8.1	8.1
			0	9.8	9.2	9.2
			1	9.5	8.6	8.5
Control	Water	NA	2	9.6	8.7	8.4
			3	9.5	9	8.9

Evaluation of insecticides for regulatory treatments of Box Tree Moth (BTM), *Cydalima perspectalis*. WP-9

APHIS-PPQ-S&T Forest Pest Management Laboratory

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Introduction

The recent incursions of the box tree moth (BTM) into several states in the United States are a significant threat to existing plantings of ornamental boxwood in residences, public gardens, and urban landscapes if it were allowed to spread. BTM larvae typically cause complete defoliation and feed on the bark of boxwood, leading to their death. Boxwood is a well-established ornamental in the U.S. and carries a high potential economic loss and considerable replacement costs. Forty-four U.S. states produce boxwood, with an estimated total annual value of \$140 million. Box tree moth has been detected in four States: Massachusetts, Michigan, New York, and Ohio. Having effective BTM insecticide treatments to protect boxwood plants in U.S. nursery production systems will be important to safeguard production facilities and to allow for the safe movement of boxwood plants free from BTM infestation.

In 2022, PPQ and its cooperators began working on the evaluation of insecticide treatment options for box tree moth to provide the data needed to support the selection of regulatory treatments for use in a BTM nursery certification program as well as to make recommendations for materials to be used for IPM treatments in nurseries and landscape environments. There are many active ingredients registered in the United States for control of lepidopteran pests in ornamentals but few of these have been evaluated for control of BTM so there was a need to evaluate these materials to make reliable recommendations for effective treatments of BTM.

The goal of this work was to provide information in support of the regulatory efforts by the USDA to control and manage the spread of this pest. Here we report the results of a series of experiments conducted to document the treatment efficacy of several candidate BTM insecticides to support treatment recommendations for the BTM cooperative program.

Methods

In the spring of 2023, candidate insecticides were evaluated for BTM control for both regulatory and IPM treatments of boxwood nursery plants. The materials chosen for the first phase of the work were those with known efficacy against lepidopteran pests with a focus on those likely to have a long period of residual control. Others were chosen for their potential to fit into existing IPM programs and to provide growers material with a wide variety of treatment options (Table 1).

There were three sets of experiments, two were based in the FPML containment facility using laboratory-reared insects that were either put on excised boxwood foliage shoots and treated to estimate direct control efficacy or plants were treated first and then challenged artificial infestations of BTM to evaluate the duration of residual control efficacy for up to a week after treatment.

The last group of experiments was conducted at a field location in New York. Boxwood nursery plants were infested with field-collected BTM larvae, then treated with candidate insecticides to evaluate their efficacy to simulate treatments that would be conducted in a nursery environment.

Table 1. Insecticides tested for regulatory treatment of BTM on boxwood foliage or plants.

Product	Active ingredient	IRAC Class	Target Site	Mode of Action	Rate
Conserve SC	spinosad	5	nicotinic Site 1	Nerve/Muscle	6 oz/100 gal
Acelepryn	chlorantraniliprole	28	Ryanodine receptors	Nerve/Muscle	16 oz/100gal
Scimitar GC	Lambda-cyhalothrin	3	Sodium channel	Nerve/Muscle	5 oz/100gal
Intrepid 2F	methoxy fenozide	18	Ecdysone agonist	IGR	8 oz/100gal
Talstar P	Bifenthrin	3	Sodium channel	Nerve/Muscle	10 & 21.7* oz/100gal
Astro	permethrin	3	Sodium channel	Nerve/Muscle	5 oz/100 gal

* Rate used on September 2023 field test.

Quarantine laboratory BTM insecticide treatments on boxwood shoots

Boxwood foliage is glossy and repels water, so a wetting agent (CapSil adjuvant; 0.12 oz/gal) was used to facilitate spreading, penetration, and adhesion of all spray applications to boxwood foliage. Insects were provided at regular intervals from the FPML colony. Table 1 lists the active ingredient, IRAC chemical class, mode of action and mix rate for each insecticide. Initial testing on the BTM egg stage included eight to ten replicates of one to two egg masses that were laid on cut sprigs of boxwood placed in floral foam in 1 oz deli cups (Fig. 1). Hatch and survival were noted after 3 days.

Testing of newly hatched (neonates) larvae was accomplished by pinning a leaf containing unhatched egg masses to the sprig bunches (Fig. 3). Following hatch, larvae moved naturally off that leaf and were then exposed to foliage that had been treated 2 to 3 days prior. This stage of the insect is very fragile and transferring them with a brush to treated foliage would result in high mortality. There were 10-15 replicates for each insecticide and assessments were done 3 days post-hatch.

The second and third larval instars can be easily transferred onto new plants, so 10 larvae per sprig bunch were placed on foliage that had been treated and dried for one hour in the laboratory hood. There were 10-15 replicates for each insecticide and instar stage and assessments were extended to seven days post-placement to verify mortality.

Another approach tested was to expose 2nd instar larvae to sprig bunches collected from boxwood plants that had been treated 4 and 7 days prior. The plants were treated outside and allowed to remain in the sun and weather. Fifty larvae were placed on sprig bunches for each of the insecticides and timings and mortality were assessed after 7 days.

Figure 1. Sprig bunches of boxwood foliage used in quarantine laboratory testing.

Figure 2. Neonates of box tree moth beginning to feed following hatch (closed eggs are translucent disks). On the right, pinned leaf with an egg mass attached to treated sprig bunch.

Field Testing BTM insecticide treatments

In July and September of 2023, two experiments of a field evaluation of the five BTM regulatory insecticide treatment candidates were conducted in an abandoned boxwood production nursery within the BTM quarantine areas in Niagara County, New York. For each experiment, BTM larvae were collected from infested boxwood in the nursery and placed on 24 untreated *Buxus microphylla* 'Winter Gem' grown in 3-gallon pots and allowed to settle and feed for 2-3 days until application. Each experiment, consisted of 6 groups of 4 boxwood plants that were placed closely together in an open grassy field, with pots and foliage touching to simulate groups of plants that are collected in staging areas before treatment (Fig. 3). Each group of plants were spaced about 1 m apart in 4 plant blocks and arrayed using a completely randomized design. The five insecticide and control treatments were randomly assigned to each group of plants. We calibrated a Solo handpump 2-gallon tank sprayer, pressurized at ~ 30 PSI, by measuring the amount of time it took to spray a group of 4 plants to run-off. In a period of 60 s, ~676-700 ml of spray mix was applied to each group of 4 plants for both experiments. For each control group, 700 ml of water was applied to the control group of plants. An adjustable cone nozzle was used for all experiments using a medium-fine droplet setting. The wetting agent CapSil was used at the rate of 0.12 oz/gal for all insecticide applications. The water sensitive spray cards were examined immediately after treatment to estimate the percent coverage of treated foliage.

Plants were censused 2 to 3 days after treatment as noted below for each specific experiment to count the number of dead, moribund, and live BTM larvae found on each plant.

July 2023 Experiment

24 three-gallon *B. microphylla* 'Winter Gem', plants infested with 1188 field collected BTM larvae collected on 07/21 (888) and 7/22 (300). These larvae were from the 1st generation of this season with mixed stages ranging from 1st thru 6th instar larvae (L1-L6) with an estimated 20% L1-L2, 50% L3-L4, 30% L5 & L6. One pupa was observed in the collection. Plants were infested by placement of infested sprigs or by transfer by small paint brush to the surface and interior portions of the plant in the afternoon on both collection days. Leaving an average of about 50 larvae/plant.

Plants were treated with insecticides in the afternoon on 7/24/23 with 2 water sensitive spray-cards placed in an interior and outer portion of 2 plants from each group of 4 plants. The first batch of 2 of 4 plants were censused for mortality counts from 36-48 h after treatment on 7/26/23. Plants were destructively sampled using pruning shears to inspect all the shoots and leaves from each plant. BTM larvae were classified as dead, moribund, or alive along with position as an inner shoot position, > 3 cm from the tip of the shoot, or an outer shoot position, ≤ 3 cm from the shoot tip. Moribund larvae were placed in a paper food service cup with untreated *Buxus* foliage and stored in a laboratory space to determine their fate.

Because there were a high number of survivors in one of the treatments that was an insect growth regulator (methoxyfenozide), we counted the second group of 2 plants per treatment on 7/27/23, 70 to 78 h after treatment. These moribund larvae were placed in a paper food service cup were censused on 7/28/23, 96 h after treatment.

September 2023 Experiment

On 9/14 and 9/17 1,100 and 865 mixed instar larvae were field collected for a total of 1,965. These larvae were from the 2nd generation of this season with mixed stages ranging from 1st thru 6th instar larvae with an estimated 77% L1-L2, 21% L3-L4, and 2% L5-L6. Twenty-four three-gallon *B. microphylla* 'Winter Gem', plants were infested on 9/14/23 (1,100) and 09/15 (865). Plants were infested as described above for an average of about 82 larvae/plant.

Plants were treated with the selected regulatory treatment candidate insecticides in the morning on 9/17/23 with 2 water sensitive spray-cards placed at the bottom and interior of resting on the soil facing up, for 2 plants from each group of 4 plants. Because of lower-than-expected mortality caused by the two pyrethroid insecticides (lambda-cyhalothrin and bifenthrin) in the July experiment, the rate of bifenthrin was increased to 21.7 fl. oz/100ga, the highest rate listed for lepidopteran pest on the Talstar P (bifenthrin) label.

The first batch of 2 of 4 plants were censused for mortality counts 72 h after treatment. Plants were destructively sampled as described above. BTM larvae were classified as dead, moribund, or alive along with position as an inner shoot position, > 3 cm from the tip of the shoot, or an outer shoot position, ≤ 3 cm from the shoot tip. Because we were running out of time available for this project, we completed the census of second group of plants on 9/22/23, 120 h after treatment. These data were analysed as a group for both sample dates.

Results and Conclusions

Quarantine laboratory BTM insecticide treatments on boxwood shoots

Only Lambda-cyhalothrin (Scimitar GC) had a statistically significant impact on BTM egg hatch and reduced hatch by 40% compared to the control group. None of the larvae that hatched and fed upon the treated foliage were alive at the 3-day assessment, while control group survival was 66% (Table 2).

When testing the neonate stage by attaching individual leaflets pinned to treated foliage (Fig. 2), we used between 300 to 593 egg masses for each of the treatments. Hatch rate was very high for all groups and ranged from 92.0 to 96.7%. Neonates readily moved over to the treated foliage and there was complete mortality for all treatments while survival of the control group was 96.7% at the 3-day assessment.

During testing on the 2nd instar larvae, we noted that not all the insects were clearly dead at the 3-day assessment, so a final assessment was conducted one week after exposure. Insects consistently noted as being alive had been exposed to the Intrepid (methoxyfenozide) treatment, which works as a moulting inhibitor (Table 1). All insects had attempted to molt to the 3rd instar by the second assessment. Ten replicates were used for each group. All insecticides showed complete mortality, while the control group showed 100% survival at the 7-day assessment.

The largest BTM larvae tested was the 3rd instar, and in terms of survival, these insects were the most robust. Ten larvae on 10-15 boxwood sprig bunches were used for each of the treatments and assessments were carried out 3- and 7-days post exposure. Control survival was at or near 100% and all insecticide treatments had some survivors at the 3-day assessment. Survival in the Intrepid treatment was >40%, but no live larvae were observed on the 7-day assessment on any of the treated foliage (Table 2).

Longevity of the insecticide treatments were assessed, and the results of applications made seven days prior are provided in Table 2. BTM larvae that fed upon aged foliage all succumbed by the 7-day assessments except for those on plants treated with Spinosad (Conserve) where about 1/3 of the larvae were actively feeding or moribund after seven days. This insecticide is known to break down rapidly in the sun and weather, so these results were expected.

Methoxyfenozide (Intrepid) was again slower acting but produced complete mortality at the 7-day assessment. (Table 2). A second test using foliage aged for 4 days gave similar results and is not reported here.

Table 2. Mean percent (\pm SE) BTM survival on treatments to boxwood shoots in quarantine laboratory 2023.

Product / Active	IRAC Class	Label rate used	Egg hatch ¹	Neonate survival ¹	Neonate survival ²	2nd Instar	3rd Instar	7 Days Post-Treatment
Acelepryn / chlorantraniprole	28	16 oz / 100 gal	62.5 \pm 14.4 % ab	0 \pm 0.0 % b	0 \pm 0.0 % b	0 \pm 0.0 % b	0 \pm 0.0 % b	0 \pm 0.0 % c
Conserve SC T&O / spinosad	5	6 oz / 100 gal	76.9 \pm 10.7 % ab	0 \pm 0.0 % b	0 \pm 0.0 % b	0 \pm 0.0 % b	0 \pm 0.0 % b	34 \pm 6.8 % b
Interprid 2F / methoxy fenozide	18	8 oz / 100 gal	83.3 \pm 9.9 % a	0 \pm 0.0 % b	0 \pm 0.0 % b	0 \pm 0.0 % b	0 \pm 0.0 % b	0 \pm 0.0 % c
Scimitar GC / lambda-cyhalothrin	3	5 oz / 100 gal	33.2 \pm 10.7 % b	0 \pm 0.0 % b	0 \pm 0.0 % b	0 \pm 0.0 % b	0 \pm 0.0 % b	0 \pm 0.0 % c
Talstar / bifenthrin	3	10.8 oz / 100 gal	n/a	n/a	0 \pm 0.0 % b	0 \pm 0.0 % b	0 \pm 0.0 % b	0 \pm 0.0 % c
Astro / permethrin	3	8 oz / 100 gal	41.8 \pm 6.9 % ab	0 \pm 0.0 % b	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Water control (w/CapSil)	n/a	n/a	81.0 \pm 7.3 % a	66 \pm 12.6 % a	96.7 \pm 3.3 % a	100 \pm 0.0 % a	98.7 \pm 0.9 % a	96.0 \pm 2.5 % a

Mean percent hatch or larval survival of BTM after seven days following treatments of eggs or foliage. For each column a different letter denotes a significant difference between treatments. ANOVA, Tukey HSD; F5,4.1, p<0.004 [hatch] and F5,26.2, p<0.001 (survival).

¹applications were made to eggs on foliage.

²leaflet with unhatched eggs was attached to treated foliage and neonates allowed to wander onto the leaf.

Field testing BTM insecticide treatments

For the July 2023 experiment, the water sensitive spray cards showed 100% coverage. The two assay dates and the final collected moribund larvae assay were analyzed as a single group. Larvae that had been

classified as moribund in the first two assays that were still alive at the final assay were counted as survivors. Because there was a wide distribution of larval stages included in the assay, mortality was analyzed as small vs. large larvae. Small larvae included the 1st-3rd instar larvae while the large larvae included the 4th-6th instar larvae. Mortality caused by chlorantraniliprole (Acelepryn) and methoxyfenozide (Intrepid) was high for both small and large larvae ranging from 98 to 100% and was significantly different from the control (Table 3). There was a trend of lower mortality rates for large larvae compared to smaller larvae for the other insecticides including only 70% mortality for large larvae compared to 98% for small larvae for the spinosad (Conserve) treatment but these were not statistically significant (Table 3).

Notably the treatments with bifenthrin (Talstar P) and lambda-cyhalothrin (Scimitar) had much lower mortality rates than the other materials, for both small and large larvae an effect that was greater for the large larvae. For lambda-cyhalothrin, this was statistically significant (Table 3). It is not clear why this occurred when high rates of mortality for these two pyrethroids was high in laboratory testing and these materials are generally very effective against other lepidopteran pests. One possible factor was there about 1/3 of an inch of rain on the day of treatment some of which came after the applications were made which may have washed off some of the residues. We also found we had used a rate for bifenthrin which was not the top label rate listed for lepidopteran pests on the Talstar P label. The difference between mortality rates for small and large larvae of some lepidopteran pest has been noted for some broad-spectrum pesticides in the literature. This may also have played a contributing factor in these results.

For the September 2023 experiments, examination of the water sensitive spray cards showed 100% coverage. All instars were analyzed as a single group since there were only a small number that were in the large larvae category. Mortality of most of the materials was high and ranged from 93-100% and was significantly different from the control (Table 4). The mortality rate for methoxyfenozide was much lower than the other treatments at 74% (Table 4). This was in contrast to the July experiments and the work performed in the quarantine laboratory. As noted above, methoxyfenozide is an insect growth regulatory and the assay time for the September experiment was too short of time for the full mortality effects to be noted.

Table 3 .Mortality of field collected BTM larvae in July 2023 field test in Niagara County New York.

Treatment	Label rate used	Percent mortality (\pm SE)	
		Small Larvae*	Large Larvae*
Acelepryn/chlorantraniliprole	16 oz / 100 gal	99.0% (0.96) a	97.5 (2.5) a
Conserve SC/spinosad	6 oz / 100 gal	0.9788 (1.24) a	70.2 (14.8) a
Intrepid/methoxyfenozide	8 oz / 100 gal	100 a	93.8 (3.6) a
Scimitar GC/lambda-cyhalothrin	5 oz / 100 gal	74.4 (4.16) a	46.8 (18.9) ab
Talstar P/bifenthrin	10.8 oz / 100 gal	90.9 (9.1) ab	59.08 (17.1) a
Water control (w/CapSil)	n/a	7.32 (3.2) c	1.9 (1.3) b

*For each treatment, a different letter denotes a significant difference. Small larvae: ANOVA, Tukey HSD; ($F_{5,18} = 69.2, p < 0.0001$); Large larvae ANOVA, Tukey HSD; ($F_{5,18} = 8.3, p < 0.0003$).

Table 4. Mortality of field collected of mixed collection of small & large BTM larvae in September 2023 field test in Niagara County New York.

Treatment	Label rate used	Percent mortality (\pm SE)*
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Acelepryn/chlorantraniliprole	16 oz / 100 gal	96.6 (3.4) a
Conserve SC/spinosad	6 oz / 100 gal	100 a
Intrepid/methoxyfenozide	8 oz / 100 gal	67.4 (7.9) b
Scimitar GC/lambda-cyhalothrin	5 oz / 100 gal	93.3 (2.5) a
Talstar P/bifenthrin	21.7 oz / 100 gal	98.2 (1.9) a
Water control (w/CapSil)	n/a	1.68 (1.1) c

*For each treatment, a different letter denotes a significant difference. ANOVA, Tukey HSD ($F_{5,18} = 64.07$, $p < 0.0001$).

Summary

Five insecticides registered for leaf-feeding caterpillars were tested for contact and residual control of box tree moth larvae in laboratory and field settings. Early instars of box tree moth larvae were consistently controlled at high label rates after treatment after direct contact applications in replicated laboratory and field experiments. Four of these materials, chlorantraniliprole, bifenthrin, methoxyfenozide, and lambda-cyhalothrin were also shown to have high residual control ranging from 90 to 100% 7 days after treatment which makes them important as regulatory treatments in boxwood production nurseries especially in areas where BTM pest pressure may be high.

All of these materials also had direct efficacy against eggs though not at a high level. However, when combined with highly efficacious residual control effects that will kill emerging neonate larvae, BTM egg masses on boxwood nursery plants can be effectively controlled along with early-stage larvae. It should be noted that for methoxyfenozide, an insect growth regulator, it takes a few days for the larvae to completely die meaning an inspection soon after treatment would appear ineffective. Methoxyfenozide may require an allowance for the time lag if it is used for a regulatory control under conditions requiring a post-treatment inspection.

Field treatments of mixed larval instar populations were also nearly as highly effective as when tested in laboratory testing. The caveat being that mixed populations of larvae with older stages may be a little harder to compare to the 1st and 3rd instars larvae tested in the laboratory study. Rain washing of some of the pesticides may have also played a role in the July study. And although we measured 100% coverage by spray cards for both the July and September studies, the 3-gallon boxwood plants are much denser with foliage and boxwood shoots making it less likely 100% coverage was achieved compared to the treatment of boxwood shoot in the laboratory testing. Still, efficacy exceeded 93% for the best materials in the September trials in conditions intended to be similar to boxwood production nurseries.

The use of a spray adjuvant improves coverage and penetration into the dense canopy and waxy foliage of boxwoods. Additional work is planned to investigate reduced application rates and additional insecticides so that growers have several treatment options and to evaluate more insecticides with systemic control properties, to evaluate new insecticides with novel modes of action, and to support of IPM programs and allow options for rotating classes of insecticides to help prevent development of resistance by BTM.

Figure 3. (a) Infesting boxwood nursery plants with field collected BTM. (b) Insecticide treatment of groups of four 3-gallon boxwood plants.

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Developing Additional Regulatory Treatments for Box Tree Moth

Executive Summary

Eight insecticides from four different modes of action were tested for efficacy and mortality against the leaf feeding caterpillars of the box tree moth (BTM), a recent invasive pest of boxwood plants in the United States. Products were assessed on the day of treatment using low labeled rates and longevity of the applications was determined for both low and high labeled rates. Efficacy of the products were assessed by exposing 3rd instar BTM larvae to treated and untreated foliage. Caterpillars were allowed to feed for 3 and 7 days before mortality assessments.

Initial screening identified poor performance against BTM by one of synthetic pyrethrins. Most of the products performed very well up to 3 weeks post-treatment when applied at the maximum labeled rate. Seven days of feeding on treated foliage was an accurate gauge of impact, especially with the product that is a molting agonist. Maximum rate of a synthetic pyrethrin and the neonicotinoid product performed poorly, but the remaining products tested were still completely effective 3 weeks post treatment.

Box tree moth larvae are readily killed with many of the insecticides commonly used against leaf-feeding caterpillars. Including a spray adjuvant improves coverage and penetration into the dense canopy and waxy foliage of boxwoods.

Background

Following a recent arrival in the US, little information is available concerning pesticide efficacy for the box tree moth (BTM), *Cydalima perspectalis*, a lepidopteran pest of boxwood plants. Results from testing conducted in 2023 of insecticide products against eggs and young larvae at the Forest Pest Methods Laboratory (FPML) quarantine facility is available (Lewis, 2024). The goal of this work was to expand the number and variety of protects tested from the prior year and to determine treatment longevity in support of the regulatory efforts by the USDA to control and manage the spread of this pest.

Figure 1. Sprig bunches of boxwood foliage used to expose insects to treated foliage.

Methods

For each product/rate tested this year, seven 3rd instar larvae were infested on five boxwood ‘bunches’ (Fig 1) and assessed after 3 and 7 days of feeding. Cuttings of ‘Winter Gem’ boxwood plants were used and insects were exposed to foliage once it had dried. At the 7 day assessment, any insect that was not clearly alive/dead was kept in a petri dish with fresh foliage and if larvae fed actively they were noted as being alive.

Weekly testing was done at FPML from mid-May to mid-September using colony insects. Table 1 lists the active ingredient, IRAC chemical class, mode of action and rates used for each insecticide. The first round of testing exposed insects on the day of treatment to the low labeled rate. The second round tested low and high labeled rates applied to outdoor plants in 3-gallon

Figure 2. Winter Gem boxwood used for treatment longevity studies in 2024.

Work Package 10: Conduct studies to determine the radiation biology of BTM to evaluate the feasibility of the sterile insect technique

Radiation Biology for Sterile Insect Technique. WP-10

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ABSTRACT

Doses of ionizing radiation that sterilize female BTM and reduce fertility of males and their offspring were investigated as a foundation for a sterile-insect release program. Pharate adults were exposed to ionizing radiation in a ^{60}CO irradiator and crossed with unirradiated adults of the opposite sex in 30-cm³ cages containing six pairs of moths. Females were exposed to doses of 80, 100, 120, 130, and 140 Gy, while males were exposed to 120, 200, 280, and 360 Gy; results were compared with unirradiated controls. Numbers of viable and non-viable eggs were recorded for 9 days, and females were dissected to determine mated status. Offspring of irradiated males and control females were reared to determine the extent of inherited sterility when they were backcrossed to unirradiated mates. Females were fully sterilized when exposed to 130 Gy. Male sterility increased from 63 to 78% of eggs compared with 40% in the control, and the proportion of mated females remained similar to the controls (87 – 92%) but declined at the highest dose (78%). Offspring of males irradiated with 120 and 200 had ~5% residual fertility. Based on these results, an optimal radiation dose for BTM is proposed between 130 and 200 Gy. Further studies will be made in larger laboratory/greenhouse cages to ensure male competitiveness and estimate effective overflooding ratios of irradiated to wild males.